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Disclaimer

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Executive Summary

The primary objective of this document is to provide a comprehensive overview of the progress made during the second year of the SMARTNESS ERC. Following the structure and research strand organization of the first scientific report, this document emphasizes the scientific aspects, highlighting key achievements and areas for improvement. Technical details of the reported activities can be found in the scientific publications listed in this document and referenced throughout the description of work.

This document follows the traditional FAPESP guidelines for annual scientific reports.¹ Its structure mirrors that of the first-year scientific report and is organized as follows:

- Section I provides a summary of the project as originally conceived, including an abstract, objectives, and expected results;
- Section II forms the core of the report, detailing the achievements during the reporting period. It begins with an executive overview highlighting key accomplishments and indicators, followed by a discussion of the engineering research approach and its impact. Activities are then presented per Work Package (WP) within each Research Strand (RS). Subsequent subsections briefly address related activities, including laboratory infrastructure, Education and Dissemination of Knowledge (EDK) initiatives, Technology Transfer (TT) efforts, and aspects of Management, Structure, and Governance (GEO). For a more detailed account of EDK, TT, and GEO activities, readers are directed to their respective reports;
- Section III outlines the institutional support received by SMARTNESS;
- Section IV provides a compilation of all publications produced during the period;
- Section V contains a list of abbreviations;
- Section VI presents the bibliography.

¹ This document is the public version of Yearly Scientific Report #02 (RC2), submitted in April 2025 and approved by FAPESP. It contains the same content as the full report, excluding three administrative sections: (i) the activity plan for the upcoming period; (ii) descriptions of participation in scientific events using FAPESP funds; and (iii) references to individual scholarship summary reports.

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I. Project Summary

A. Abstract

The SMARTNESS Engineering Research Center (ERC) targets developing cutting-edge advances in communication networks and digital application services scoped in strategic areas where significant scientific and technological impacts can be achieved towards 2030, in collaboration with the cloud and networking research communities. As 5G releases roll-out and the vision on 6G is being developed, the main challenge of SMARTNESS is how to engineer (i.e. design and operate) cloud computing and network infrastructures with the adequate capabilities to empower next-generation Internet services and applications. The scope of end-to-end Internet-scale services is exceptionally broad and requires contributions from various disciplines along with large capital and human resource investments. However, the ongoing digital transformation in vertical industries and a shift towards open source network softwarization and disaggregation of infrastructures at multiple levels and protocol stack layers have opened well-scoped opportunities for accelerated innovation at unprecedented entry barriers for research enterprises based on academic and industrial partnerships. Cloud computing and network infrastructures are increasingly becoming more multidisciplinary, requiring system-oriented end-to-end views that leverage advances in Hardware (HW) for computing and networking, modern Software (SW) architectures, machine intelligence (AI/ML), user interfaces, "as a Service" consumption and new business models, among other engineering disciplines (e.g., energy efficiency and design for security). SMARTNESS aims at exploiting well-thought-out opportunities through a proper methodology based on the confluence of parallel Research Strands (RS) tailored for successful impact research and innovation at world-class levels towards the realization of challenging use cases in Internet scenarios for industry and society with a 2030 horizon view.

B. Objectives

SMARTNESS has the ambitious objective to go beyond the state-of-the-art in several networked system disciplines, clustered into five areas of Scientific and Technological Advancements (STA), namely, (i) Customized Edge Computing, (ii) Fluid Control & Data Planes, (iii) Cognitive Architectures, (iv) Trustworthiness - Security, Privacy, Safety, Ethics, and (v) Sustainability. Each STA includes specific objectives within a common theme, acting as building blocks upon which research strands (RS) are defined and executed as the chosen strategy to organize research and engineering efforts. Each RS encompasses a group of well-defined timely STA research objectives to realize exemplary use case applications. SMARTNESS will start and be supported by currently deployed technologies and infrastructures that will evolve throughout the RS execution. The SMARTNESS view on growing the technology readiness levels is based on a deep study of already existing solutions, focusing on the technical gaps and challenges to harden the initial requirements of each RS, and validate the final approach by deep experimentation with running prototypes and experimental evaluation embodied in selected pilots. Each RS has a lifecycle, where new RS are built considering outputs from previously ended RS and inputs from the updated mid- and long-term visions, external feedback from project reviewers and the scientific community, guidance from the International Advisory Board (IAB), among other forces expected to contribute to the most appropriate steering of active RS and the definition of new ones. The RS identified for the initial years of SMARTNESS are as follows: NEWTON: iN Edge netWork indusTrial automatioN, (2) DEMIST: Distributed Edge Computing Swarm Intelligence, (3) C3LA: Cognitive Closed Control Loops Architecture for Edge IoV Services, (4) ADVENTURE: Adaptive and Secure Network Applications over the Industrial Internet, and (5) DisCoNet: Distributed Computer Networking.

C. Expected Results

SMARTNESS is expected to achieve impact results in Brazil and abroad from a four-axis perspective: technological and scientific, standardization, socio-economic, and commercial.

- **International technological and scientific impact.** The results achieved by SMARTNESS will be disseminated through open source software, open data, software APIs, high-quality scientific publications in high impact vehicles, industry-academia workshops and integration with existing solutions. The dissemination activities will result in a significant increase in the number of citations to SMARTNESS scientific productions and partnerships with renowned researchers and research centers world-wide. Outcomes of each RS will be embodied in Proof of Concept (PoC) implementations validated through experimental evaluation and testbed demos.
- **Standardization impact.** SMARTNESS will contribute to selected standards development organization (e.g., ONF, IETF, ITU-T, 3GPP, ONAP, O-RAN, and ETSI) activities in terms of architectures and PoC implementations. Concepts, technical solutions, and open source software produced by SMARTNESS will contribute to the current and upcoming IP-related standards.
- **Socio-economic impact.** SMARTNESS will be the first center focused on smart networks and services in Brazil towards the realization of killer novel applications such as robotics, vehicular networks, AR/VR/XR, holographic communication, all of them natively integrated with ML and cognitive artifacts. All of these areas are key to the future of technological innovation in the country as they are directly related to the future of mobile telecommunications networks towards 6G, which should shape the services and applications of telecom companies in the coming years. The training of human resources undergraduate, graduate, including interactions with mid/high school students, will generate new careers in the upfronting areas and positively impact the local ecosystem, both in terms of improvement of services available to the population and new opportunities for young researchers in São Paulo and Brazil.
- **Commercial impact.** It is expected that part of the results achieved by SMARTNESS will be absorbed by governments and industries, especially in the B5G ecosystem, certainly but not limited to Ericsson units, through innovation in products, new business models, and startups. The support from additional FAPESP funding lines, in the form of the PIPE and PITE programs that can be incubated within the SMARTNESS center, will contribute to the impact setting of this objective. We foresee that SMARTNESS testbed infrastructures, realistic network, and user emulation capabilities in scope of 5G and beyond could welcome hosting startups experiments for validation and stress testing of end-user and server-side software applications under realistic environments, integrated with programmable networks and the advanced network services in scope of the proposed research strands.

II. Achievements in the period

A. Executive Overview

As it reaches its second year, the SMARTNESS ERC stands at a stage of consolidation and deeper exploration of its research, showcasing both the scientific and technological progress made and the challenges encountered along the way. This document records this trajectory, offering a detailed summary of the progress achieved during this phase. It examines the methodologies applied, the obstacles faced, and the adjustments introduced to enhance research efficiency. Additionally, it situates the achievements within the broader scientific and technological landscape, emphasizing its influence on engineering advancements and interdisciplinary collaboration. By addressing the technical and organizational dimensions of the initiative, this document provides insights into the tangible impacts generated and outlines the planned directions for the project's next steps.

To provide an overview of Y2 progress, this report is organized into the following thematic sections:

Overview of SMARTNESS Engineering Research Approach & Impact: the introduction delineates the structured organization of SMARTNESS covering distinct Scientific and Technological Advancements (STA), systematically arranged within Research Strands (RS) that serve as hosts to various Work Packages (WP). SMARTNESS RS serve as core organizational framework for structuring research and engineering initiatives towards focused, time-bound STA objectives, which are implemented through dedicated WPs that target use-case applications. During Y2, SMARTNESS has refined its execution strategy, adapting RS to incorporate new research demands, integrate emerging technologies, and address increasingly complex use cases. [\[Section II.B\]](#)

Research Strands activities per Work Package: this section presents the core technical activities and achievements during the second year, tracking the evolution of RS WP across different stages (completed, ongoing, newly initiated, and upcoming). Within this context, it provides a structured overview of all WPs, highlighting key research developments, team contributions, and their continuous adaptation of objectives, alongside principal findings and scientific publication results. [\[Section II.C\]](#)

Lab Infrastructures & Testbeds: this section details the advancements in establishing an experimental environment for SMARTNESS. Renovations are underway to accommodate the main laboratory at LEMAC-FEEC, integrating cutting-edge measurement facilities such as a full anechoic chamber and high-frequency VNAs. Additionally, the section presents progress on the deployment of a private 5G SA network, ongoing infrastructure upgrades, and the expansion of computational and networking resources to support research activities. [\[Section II.D\]](#)

Education and Dissemination of Knowledge (EDK): this section summarizes the main efforts and accomplishments in the Year 2 EDK Report (REDK2) that explores in detail all ongoing initiatives and achievements in scientific engagement, workforce development, and outreach within the research community, including contributions to high-impact publications, participation in and organization of major scientific events, and integration of new educational resources. [\[Section II.E\]](#)

Technology Transfer (TT): this section presents an abstract of TT efforts during the second year, which are detailed in the TT Report (RTT2) and span open research, standardization, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), research spin-offs, and technological knowledge transfer. [\[Section II.F\]](#)

Management, Structure and Governance (GEO): this section recaps the essence of the management, structure, and governance practices of SMARTNESS, all of which are detailed in the Year 2 GEO report (RGEO2), covering the center's organizational framework, quality assurance protocols, risk management strategies, communication tools, and administrative procedures. The second year's efforts highlight the consolidation of the organizational structure, the implementation of

more efficient review processes, the expansion of communication channels, and the establishment of workflows that enhance internal coordination and decision-making. [\[Section II.G\]](#)

Institutional Support: this section outlines the institutional support that has strengthened SMARTNESS activities throughout its second year, including research management, administrative assistance, communication strategies, IPR management, and laboratory infrastructure. Notable developments include expanding the management team through PPDG grants, additional financial support for laboratory renovations via the InfraPeq program, and ongoing assistance from different institutional entities. [\[Section III\]](#)

List of publications. [Section IV](#) presents the list of publications resulting from SMARTNESS activities. The reference style for the publications produced in year 02 uses the RC2 prefix followed by the publication category index recommended by FAPESP, which are reproduced below.

- A – Papers in indexed scientific periodicals
- B – Papers in non-indexed scientific periodicals
- C – Papers presented in international conferences
- D – Papers presented in Brazilian conferences
- E – Patents requested or obtained
- F – Chapters in published books
- G – Books published
- H – MSc Dissertations defended
- I – PhD Theses defended
- J – List of papers prepared, submitted, and accepted for publication

For in-text citations of non-SMARTNESS publications, a variation of the Chicago author-date reference style is adopted for bibliography quotations of the works in the **References** ([Section VI](#)). Square brackets are used to encompass author names and publication years. For papers with more than three authors, the abbreviation “et al.” (Latin for “and others”) is used to shorten the citation space. [Section V](#) provides a **List of Abbreviations** used in this report.

■ Highlights & Indicators

Beyond individual achievements, the Center’s second-year progress reflects a systemic maturation that creates a self-sustaining research ecosystem. These structural enablers have directly catalyzed different highlights and notable key performance indicators as outlined next:

- **Open Science:** In its second year, the SMARTNESS ERC strengthened its commitment to open science by expanding the dissemination of research outputs across multiple platforms. The SMARTNESS website was extensively utilized to share scientific publications, ensuring broad accessibility to research findings, while institutional data repositories like UNICAMP’s REDU were adopted following revised post-graduate program regulations and FAPESP guidelines for structured data management. Research software and datasets were systematically published on GitHub, providing direct access to implementation codes, experimental results, and tools supporting ongoing RS WPs. A key milestone in these efforts was the adoption of Zenodo as a central repository, where the SMARTNESS community has started to store all scientific publications, technical presentations, demonstration materials, and open research artifacts. This structured repository ensures that research products are easily accessible, properly archived, and publicly available for the wide research community.
- **Management Team:** A significant development in SMARTNESS’s second year was the expansion of its Management Team, made possible through the UNICAMP/PRP Support

Program for the Management of Large Thematic Research Centers (Resolution CEPE-A-001/2024). This initiative was designed to enhance the operational infrastructure of major research centers by bringing in specialized professionals for strategic management roles. As part of this effort, SMARTNESS welcomed three dedicated postdoctoral fellows, each assuming responsibility for a key management area: Technology Transfer (TT), Education and Dissemination of Knowledge (EDK), and Executive Management, altogether contributing to smooth coordination of project execution and administrative processes.

- **Awareness to the national and international communities:** SMARTNESS expanded its presence in networking and cloud computing through scientific presentations of research results and institutional presentations in multiple events. SMARTNESS has actively engaged with the scientific community beyond mere awareness-building, fostering active participation and contributions in terms of publications, demonstrations, tutorials, among others. Through the organization and participation in prominent scientific events such as the 2024 editions of SBRC, IEEE NOMS, NetSoft, NFV-SDN, SMARTNESS has significantly advanced knowledge in its respective field. More details on SMARTNESS awareness can be found in REDK2.
- **Scientific Progress:** During the second year, SMARTNESS continued to advance its research activities across multiple Work Packages (WPs) and Research Strands (RSs), further solidifying its scientific impact. The initiative now involves 15+ senior researchers and has supported over 35 scholarships, including 5 postdoctoral fellows, 15 PhD candidates, 7 MSc students, and 9 undergraduate research projects, funded through FAPESP, FUNCAMP, and PRP. Additionally, 3 MSc theses and 2 PhD dissertations were successfully defended during this period. While the size and maturity of WPs vary, most have established well-structured operational practices, including bi-weekly meetings with Ericsson researchers, dedicated workspaces, and effective communication channels. The scientific progress achieved through these efforts continues to generate tangible results, as detailed in the following sections.
- **Intellectual Property and Technology Transfer:** The culture of intellectual property (IP) and technology transfer (TT) continues to be fostered among researchers and students through regular RS WP meetings and the SMARTNESS Hour. During the annual workshop, IPR and TT considerations are presented, and common questions are clarified. A recorded session on general IPR practices, as well as those specific to SMARTNESS, is included in the "welcome pack" for all new members. As of this report, three Invention Disclosures (IvDs) have been submitted, and one international PCT patent has been filed.

Tables 1 to 5 present key performance indicators (KPIs) and impact targets, along with their status after Year 2, across different strategic areas to assess the success as originally envisioned.

Table 1. Dissemination & Exploitation impact setting activities and KPIs.

Activity	Target KPI	Realized in Y2	Total Y1 + Y2
Scientific Publications	At least 2 papers/peer-reviewed articles acknowledging SMARTNESS per year per Research Strand	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 03 scientific periodicals 20 international conferences 14 Brazilian conferences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 05 scientific periodicals 31 international conferences 16 Brazilian conferences
Open Source Software	1 per Research Strand, if applicable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 10 public repositories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 15+ repositories
Open Data Repository	1 per Research Strand, if applicable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 01 new dataset: VR-AR-CG Network Traffic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 04 datasets
Standardization	At least 2 contributions (e.g. co-authoring of drafts, presentations) per year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2 leadership positions: Vice-Chair of ITC (IEEE ComSoc & ISOC), Executive Coordinator of IT at USP 4 participations in standardization committees (ABNT & ANATEL) 1 quality system implementation: ISO 17025:2017 for research & technology transfer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Idem</i> Y2
Intellectual Property	At least 4 contributions (e.g. co-authoring of IVD, patent filings) per year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 02 IVDs submitted 01 patent filed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 03 IVDs submitted 01 patent filed
Spin-offs pitches	After the 3rd year, at least 1 every two years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 01 spin-off framework (under development) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 01 spin-off framework (under development)
Collaboration with startups	1 every three years	NTR (Nothing To Report)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 01 Support letter to PITE submission

Table 2. Publication KPIs per type and status in Y2 and total after the first two years.

Publication Type / Status	Published	Accepted	Submitted	Published (Y1 + Y2)
A) Papers in indexed scientific periodicals	3	0	3	5
B) Papers in non-indexed scientific periodicals	0	0	0	0
C) Papers in international conferences	20	8	2	31
D) Papers in Brazilian conferences	14	4	1	16
E) Patents	0	0	1	0
F) Book Chapters	3	0	0	3
G) Books	0	0	0	3
H) MSc Dissertations defended	3			6
I) PhD Theses defended	2			2
Total	45	12	7	66

Table 3. Dissemination activities in the scope of the communication plan and KPIs.

Activity	Target KPI	Realized in Y2
Website content	At least 5 new content items/month; 1 whitepaper/year summarizing the main achievements/progress report	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 43 Posts on News • 38 Scientific publications • 05+ Scholarships Opportunities • 02 Presentations • 04 Newsletters • 01 Events • 04 Software
Webinars, podcasts and short videos	6 / year, with researchers from the consortium or outside 1 institutional video about the Center	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 02 short videos (SMARTNESS First Annual Workshop, Welcome Day at FEEC 2024)
Social media dissemination	At least 4 posts/month in social media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 63 Posts on Facebook • 65 Posts on Instagram • 04 Reels on Instagram • 27 Stories on Instagram • 71 Posts in LinkedIn • 39 Posts in Twitter

Table 4. Scientific & Educational Events impact setting activities and KPIs.

Activity	Target KPI	Realized in Y2
Summer Schools	At least 1 / year, co-located with national/international conferences or on the premises of the Universities / Ericsson	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 01 bootcamp prepared to be held during the week of Y2 workshop
Hackathons (Technological + Educational)	2 / year, co-located with national/international conferences or on the premises of the Universities / Ericsson	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NTR (Nothing To Report)
Open Scientific Challenge	1 every two years. Public with worldwide participation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NTR (Nothing To Report)
One-day workshops (Technological + Educational)	2 / year, co-located with national/international conferences and/or on the premises of the Universities / Ericsson	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 01 Workshop in SBRC 2024: Workshop de Redes Quânticas (WQuNets) • 01 Yearly Workshop (Apr/2024)
Co-Organization and Participation in scientific events	At least 3 per year per Research Strand	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 04 co-organization of workshops in scientific events • 10+ Participation in events.
Participation in renowned industrial exhibitions	At least 1 / year (depending on the industrial exhibitions agenda)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 04: Futurecom 2024; 6G Briefing 2024, Campinas Innovation Week 2024, WARAP-PS Week 2024.
Ericsson Research Open Day	1 every two years, open house day at Ericsson in Brazil (São Paulo or Indaiatuba)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 01: Talk + 5 demos of WP results (Sep/2024, Indaiatuba)

Table 5. Teaching, Training & Workforce Development activities and KPIs.

Activity	Target KPI	Realized in Y2
Teaching: New/adapted academic courses	At least 20 courses will be impacted or created, both graduate and undergraduate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 04 grad courses impacted • 01 extension course impacted
Teacher training	1 every two years, short seminars for pre-college teachers	NTR (Nothing To Report)
Pre-college in-class and out-of-class activities	1 / year, short seminars to pre-college students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 01 pre-college program/education dissemination project launched (Dr. Telêmaco Paioli Melges State School)
FAPESP São Paulo School of Advanced Science	1 every three years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NTR (Nothing To Report)
Workforce Development	On average, per RS (approx. 5 active in parallel at any given time): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 Postdoc (PD) per year, • 2 PhD (DR) every 4 years, • 2 MSc (MS) every 2 years, • 1 Undergrad (UG) project per year 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 03 MSc defenses. • 02 PhD defenses. <p>Current size in terms of active scholarships:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PD: 05 • DR: 15 • MS: 12 • UG: 09

B. Introduction to SMARTNESS Engineering Research Approach & Impact

The SMART Networks and ServiceS for 2030 (SMARTNESS) Engineering Research Center (ERC) has the ambition to go beyond the state-of-the-art networked system disciplines that can be clustered into five major areas of Scientific and Technological Advancements (STA), namely, (i) Customized Edge Computing, (ii) Fluid Control & Data Planes, (iii) Cognitive Architectures, (iv) Trustworthiness - Security, Privacy, Safety, Ethics, and (v) Sustainability. As shown in Figure 1, the scope of SMARTNESS includes STA, regarded as enablers of future applications relevant to society and industry in the horizon of 2030 and the 6G time frame. The vision of SMARTNESS is to structure STAs that gather specific, ambitious objectives within a common theme, acting as building blocks upon which Research Strands (RS) are defined and executed.

Figure 1. Main areas of Scientific and Technological Advancements (STA) in the scope of SMARTNESS.

At execution time, RS act as organizational thrusts that host the work packages (WP) where the actual scientific and technological contributions in the different STAs are realized. WPs include target application domains and scenarios that challenge the state of the art in each STA realm. Figure 2 shows the SMARTNESS execution strategy based on Research Strands (RS) to organize research and engineering efforts. Each RS encompasses a group of well-defined, timely STA research objectives described in Work Packages (WP) to carry out tasks towards the realization of exemplary use case applications. SMARTNESS will start and be supported by currently deployed technologies and infrastructures evolving throughout the RS execution.

Figure 2. SMARTNESS RS / WP Management Structures and lifecycle. The left side illustrates the initial set-up with “independent” RS WPs. The right side illustrates the aggregation of RSs into new WPs to cope with more complex use cases and/or strengthen the results.

As described in the FAPESP ERC proposal of SMARTNESS, the bootstrapping RS proposed for the initial years are as follows:

- NEWTON: In Edge netWork indusTrial automatiON
- C3LA: Cognitive Closed Control Loops Architecture for Edge IoV Services
- DisCoNet: Distributed Computer Networking
- DEMIST: Distributed Edge Computing Swarm Intelligence
- ADVENTURE: Adaptive and Secure Network Applications over the Industrial Internet

As shown in Figure 3, the five RS presented in the original plan of the ERC serve to illustrate how research activities were expected to be effectively carried out within SMARTNESS. The description of RS served to motivate challenging application use case scenarios along with the research methodology towards the realization of concrete objectives per STA.

Figure 3. Exemplar illustration of SMARTNESS RS lifecycle and strawman effort distribution per STA. Not shown for clarity are the transfer/re-use of milestones across RS work packages.

As expected from any 10-year research-centric initiative, different forces were expected to contribute to the most appropriate steering of RS at run-time along with the motivation to define new RS. The SMARTNESS view on growing the technology readiness levels is based on continuous monitoring of research developments, assessments of existing solutions, and identification of technical gaps and research challenges viable to be tackled through Work Packages (WPs).

Acting as a research management structure, each RS has a natural lifecycle, where new RS is built considering outputs from previously ended RS and inputs from the updated mid- and long-term visions, external feedback from project reviewers and the scientific community, guidance from the International Advisory Board (IAB), among other research & development & innovation forces that influence WPs within RS.

Each WP takes into consideration the availability of an adequate team of investigators and students to carry out up-to-date STA objectives after a proper assessment of the state-of-the-art. Depending on the nature and size of each WP, adequate research methodology will be applied, eventually including the development of prototype implementations, testbed experiments, and evaluation of embodiments in selected pilots.

After two years of activities in the Center, we confirm that a comprehensive way of understanding our mode of operation is to draw an analogy to a push-pull strategy applied to academia-industry research

collaboration. A pull system initiates production as a reaction to present demand, whereas a push system initiates production in anticipation of future demand.

Figure 4. SMARTNESS Push-Pull model for Academia-Industry Collaboration

As illustrated in Figure 4, Academic Research *Push* brings new research findings, ideas, trends, etc., from SMARTNESS to Ericsson Research and other stakeholders at national and international scope. In the other direction, Industry & Community / Ericsson *Pull* has exercised through the sharing of new research demands/opportunities from related research projects (e.g. EU SNS JU) and/or standardization efforts (e.g. O-RAN, 3GPP) brought to SMARTNESS with the objective of provoking relevant contributions after shaping ongoing Research Strand WPs and/or creating new ones. Both the Push and Pull thrusts are carefully curated by the EC plus, where appropriate, guided by interactions with members of our scientific STA board (STAB) and advisory board (IAB).

The original impact plan of SMARTNESS is evolving as expected, with the Center poised to exert a significant influence on both the Brazilian and global contexts. Figure 5 illustrates our impact-setting approach, encompassing a multifaceted strategy including public policy, startup ventures, and societal impact, all guided by tailored exploitation plans.

Figure 5. SMARTNESS Impact Setting

C. Research Strands activities per Work Package

This section outlines the core technical activities and achievements of SMARTNESS, reviewing all RS WPs after Year 02. As expected from the Center's operational model, some WPs (e.g., NW1, CL1, DM1) have completed their planned two-year lifecycle, while others are at different stages—midway (e.g., DC2, DC3), newly initiated (e.g., NW3), or about to begin (e.g., NW4, CL3)—at the time of writing this scientific report (RC2). Consequently, the scope of reported activities varies across WPs, reflecting differences in team composition and prior research progress.

As noted in RC1 one year ago, multiple WPs are driven by XR-type application scenarios that present significant research and engineering challenges across various technological domains (cloud, networking, AI/ML), collectively known as SMARTNESS STAs. The most demanding requirements involve ensuring low end-to-end latency.

Building on early Y1 research developments related to mid-term visionary use cases in Holographic-Type Communications (HTC), a second WP was spun off from the initial C3LA WP on multimedia QoE estimation WP to focus on immersive media services. This field is expected to experience significant growth and pose considerable challenges from both networking and computing perspectives. Additionally, its use cases hold relevance for both industrial and societal applications. Furthermore, UAVs, including drones and robotics, continue to be highly relevant and are increasingly influential in driving applications. These topics are actively addressed in dedicated RS WPs. As 3GPP standardization efforts towards 6G release relevant use cases and target KPIs [3GPP TR 22.870], we expect all WPs to update their application scenarios and their expected performance and value indicators.

A schedule-centric overview of all RS WPs, regardless of their status (ended, active, or planned), is presented in Table 6. Table 7 provides details on the WP teams, including both academic and Ericsson researchers, for all WPs with reported activities during Y2.

For readability and conciseness, a standardized naming convention has been adopted to uniquely identify each WP. This convention uses a two-letter prefix representing the RS, followed by the WP number. For example, WP1 of the NEWTON RS is labeled NW1, WP1 of the C3LA RS is CL1, and WP1 of DisCoNet is DC1.

Table 6. Overview of all WPs, with Q1/2023 the official start date of the SMARTNESS ERC. Completed quarters of WP are colored in red, while upcoming quarters are in green.

RS WP#. <i>Short Name</i>	2023				2024				2025				2026			
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4												
NW1. Dataplane HW acceleration/offloading	Red	White														
NW2. Internet of Robotic Things for smart enterprises	White	White	White	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	White	White	White	White
NW3. Distributed perception at the TROCA environment	White	Red	Green													
NW4. Programmable data plane	White	Green														
CL1. Multimedia traffic modeling and QoE eval	Red	White														
CL2. Holographic Type Communications (HTC)	White	White	White	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	White						
CL3. Immersive Media	White	Green														
DC1. Disaggregation and edge offloading of XR & ML models	White	White	Red	Green	Green	White	White	White	White	White						
DC2. WebAssembly Edge Offloading of Browser Apps	White	White	White	White	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green	Green	White	White	White	White	White
DC3. O-RAN and intelligent decision-making based on DL	White	White	White	White	White	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green						
DC4. LLM-enabled control with dynamic compute AI offloading	White	Red	Green													
DM1. Video delivery at the edge with support for VR/AR	Red	White														
DM2. Edge-assisted intelligent drone management	White	White	White	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green						
DM3. Vertical Federated Learning in telco scenarios	White	Green														
AD.WP1: Network Software Testing	White	White	White	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	White						
AD.WP2: Prioritization of Smart Grid Traffic	White	White	Red	White												
AD1. Distributed Intelligence for Secure 6G Network Services	White	Green														
AD2. Blockchain-based governance mechanisms	White	White	Red	Green												

Table 7. Key facts of all WPs per RS.

RS	WP# / Theme	Academic Team	Ericsson Team
DisCoNet	1. Disaggregation and offloading of XR applications and ML models to the edge - Start: Q3-2023 - End: N/A	PI: Prof. Fabio L. Verdi (UFSCar) Co-PI: Prof. Sand (UFG) PhD 1: Guilherme Matos (UFSCar) PhD 2: Washington Silva (UFSCar)	Andrew W. (RA Compute & Software)
	2. WebAssembly Edge Offloading of Browser User Apps - Start: Q1-2024 - End: N/A	PI: Prof. Sand Luz (UFG) Co-PI: Prof. Fábio L. Verdi (UFSCar) Co-PI: Prof. Cristiano Both (Unisinos) Co-PI: Prof. Bruno Silvestre (UFG) UR 1: Gabriel Espindola (UFG) UR 2: Matheus Lucas Morais Pires (UFG) MSc: Gustavo Jardim (Unisinos)	Andrew W., Martin E., Hector C.
	3. O-RAN and intelligent decision-making based on distributed learning mechanisms - Start: Q2-2024 - End: N/A	PI: Flávio Rocha (UFG) Co-PI: Prof. Kleber Vieira Cardoso (UFG) Co-PI: Prof. Cristiano Both (Unisinos) Co-PI: Prof. Fábio L. Verdi (UFSCar) Co-PI: Prof. Leandro Almeida (UFSCar) UR 1: Marcus Leite (UFSCar) UR 2: Murilo Melo (UFG) MSc: Vlademir Brusse (UFSCar) PhD: Sergio Rossi B. da Silva (Unicamp) Post-doc: Rohi Tariq (UFSCar) [S: Q3/25]	Pedro G. (RA Networks), Maria M.
	4. LLM-enabled control with dynamic compute offloading of AI modules - Start: Q1-2025 - End: N/A	PI: Prof. Fabio Verdi (UFSCar) Co-PI: Prof. Kleber Vieira Cardoso (UFG) Co-PI: Prof. Sand (UFG) UR 1: Gabriel Espindola (UFG) UR 2: Matheus Lucas Morais Pires (UFG) UR 3: Felipe Bonadia Bravo (UFSCar) UR 4: João Vitor Naves Mesa (UFSCar)	Pedro G. and Ricardo S.
NEWTON	1. Dataplane HW acceleration/offloading of infra/app functions - Start: Q1-2023 - End: Q1-2025	PI: Prof. Christian Rothenberg (UNICAMP) Co-PI: Prof. Fabio Verdi (UFSCar) Co-PI: Prof. Marcelo Luizelli (UNIPAMPA) Post-doc: Dr. Alireza Shirmarz (UFSCar) PhD 1: Fabricio Rodriguez (UNICAMP) PhD 3: Francisco Vogt (UNICAMP) MSc 1: Arthur Simas (UNICAMP) MSc 2: Sergio Rossi (UNICAMP) MSc 3: Filipo Costa (UNICAMP) MSc 4: Felipe Novais (UFSCar) UR: Gabriel Andrade (UFSCar)	Gergely P. Gyanesh P. (RA Networks)
	2. Internet of Robotic Things (IoRT) - Start: Q4-2023 - End: N/A	PI: Prof. Eric Rohmer (UNICAMP) PhD 1: Cesar Bastos (UNICAMP) MSc 1: Breno Portela (UNICAMP) MSc 2: Ervin Bolivar (UNICAMP)	Alberto Hata (RA AI)

	3. Distributed perception at the TROCA environment - Start: Q1-2025 - End: N/A	PI: Ricardo Gudwin (UNICAMP) PhD 1: José Renato Borelli (UNICAMP) MSc 1: Victor M. Rodrigues (UNICAMP) IC 1: <i>tbd</i> (UNICAMP)	Alberto H. (RA AI)
	4. Programmable Data Plane - Start: Q2-2025 - End: N/A	PI: Prof. Christian Rothenberg (UNICAMP) PhD 1: Francisco Vogt (UNICAMP) PhD 2: Arthur Simas (UNICAMP) PhD 3: Sergio Rossi (UNICAMP) MSc 1: Filipo Costa (UNICAMP)	Gergely P. Gyanesh P. (RA Networks)
C3LA	1. Mobile Multimedia QoE evaluation - Start: Q2-2023 -- End: Q1-2025	PI: Prof. Christian Rothenberg (UNICAMP) Co-PI: Prof. Fabio Verdi (UFSCar) Post-doc: Alireza Shirmarz (UFSCar) PhD 1: Tariqul Islam (UNICAMP) PhD 2: Ariel Goes (UNICAMP) UR: Leonardo Guimarães (UNICAMP)	Gyanesh P. Szilveszter N. (RA Networks)
	2. Holographic-Type Communications (HTC) - Start: Q4-2023 - End: N/A	PI: Prof. Christian Rothenberg (UNICAMP) Co-PI: Prof. Eduardo Cerqueira (UFPA) Co-PI: Prof. Vanessa Testoni (UNICAMP) PhD 1: Marina Martinelli (UNICAMP) PhD 2: Alan Teixeira (UNICAMP) MSc 1: Rafael Clerici (UNICAMP)	Maria V. Marquezini (RA Networks)
	3. Immersive Media - Start: Q2-2025 - End: N/A	PI: Prof. Christian Rothenberg (UNICAMP) Co-PI: Prof. Vanessa Testoni (UNICAMP) Co-PI: Prof. Fabio Verdi (UFSCar) Post-doc: Alireza Shirmarz (UFSCar) PhD 1: Tariqul Islam (UNICAMP) PhD 2: Ariel Goes (UNICAMP) PhD 3: Alan Teixeira (UNICAMP) MSc 1: Rafael Clerici (UNICAMP) UR: Carlos Marques (UFSCar)	<i>tbd</i>
DEMIST	1. Edge support for (smart) AR/VR - Start: Q2-2023 - End: N/A	PI: Prof. Luiz Bittencourt (UNICAMP) Co-PI: Dr. Roger Immich (UFRN) Co-PI: Dr. Roberto Rodrigues (UFSC) PhD 1: Eduardo Gama (UNICAMP)	Mattias Wildeman Björn Skubic (RA Compute & Software)
	2. Edge-assisted intelligent drone management - Start: Q4-2023 - End: N/A	PI: Prof. Luiz Bittencourt (UNICAMP) Co-PI: Fernando von Zuben (UNICAMP) Co-PI: Fredrik Heintz (LiU) Post-doc: Fabiola Oliveira (UNICAMP) PhD 1: Mauricio Rodriguez (UNICAMP) PhD 2: Danielle Fortunato (UNICAMP) PhD3: Heictor Oliveira (UNICAMP) UR: Lucas Soares (UNICAMP) UR: Ibini Santana (UNICAMP) UR: Lucas de Araújo (UNICAMP)	Maria V. Marquezini (RA Networks) Jean Martins (RA AI)
ADVENTURE	1. Distributed Intelligence for Secure 6G Network Services - Start: Q2-2025 - End: N/A	PI: Prof. Daniel Macêdo Batista (USP) Post-Doc: <i>tbd</i> (USP) PhD: Evgeni K. C. Ortega (USP) MSc: Ana Carla Quallio Rosa (USP) MSc: Lucas Seiki Oshiro (USP) UR: Ivan Gabriel Ferreira Dias (USP)	<i>tbd</i>

		UR: Renata Meyer Hobold (USP) UR: Thiago Duvanel Ferreira (USP)	
	2. Blockchain-Based Governance - Start: Q3-2023 - End: N/A	PI: Prof. Jó Ueyama (USP) Co-PI: Prof. Marco Amaral (UNICAMP) PhD 1: Rodrigo Dutra Garcia (USP)	Pedro G. (RA Networks)

■ DisCoNet - Distributed Computer Networking

DC1: Disaggregation and edge offloading of XR apps & ML models

The evolution of software and hardware reached the point where CPUs can no longer meet (alone) the new demands of the future. To deal with this problem, new devices and paradigms have emerged, and among these devices are various programmable and non-programmable devices, like Tofino switches, SmartNICs, GPUs, DPUs, and FPGAs, which are used to perform network processing and other specialized functions [Choi et al., 2019], thus releasing the CPU to only handle applications [Firestone et al., 2018]. In line with these hardware advances, AR/VR applications promise to be a transformative technology for several fields in the upcoming years by providing new business opportunities as well as new research trends [Morin et al., 2022]. In order to deliver such market transformation, AR/VR-based applications must be able to accurately integrate physical and virtual objects in real-time, and for such, they rely on computing-intensive machine learning algorithms.

The main activities and achievements in this period can be summarized as follows:

- **Two papers were published in the ACM Conext Student Workshop 2024.** The first [RC2.C14] one is related to delivering AR to the edge by implementing object recognition through the in-network computing paradigm. The second paper [RC2.C15] refers to the functional decomposition of monolithic applications to heterogeneous hardware.
- **Visit Ericsson Research in Santa Clara, CA.** A team visited for two days Ericsson Research in Santa Clara. Several presentations were done during the visit to extend the collaboration between SMARTNESS and that research unit.
- **Design and implementation of DECOMPOSER,** a mechanism designed to decompose monolithic applications into modular components, allowing them to be executed across various combinations of hardware architectures, both locally and in distributed settings. This result will appear in the IEEE NOMS 2025 [RC2.J07].
- **PhD qualification defense** of Washington Silva, who is now preparing the workplan of a BEPE scholarship at Cardiff University.
- The IvD “Optimizing Subgraph Deployment for AI Applications” is under Ericsson's internal evaluation.

DC2: WebAssembly Edge Offloading of Browser User Apps

The goal of this WP is to understand the specific offloading requirements for a set of representative XR algorithms and processing blocks (e.g., simultaneous localization and mapping, semantic understanding algorithms, object detection algorithms, and rendering engine), determine how data flows between such algorithms, and analyze if some state information is required to be kept. Port a set of implementations (representing the algorithms studied) to WebAssembly. Design, implement, and evaluate a prototype for dynamic offloading of XR algorithms.

The main activities and achievements in this period can be summarized as follows:

- Research is being conducted on three main topics:
 - 1) increase the use of WebAssembly code in the Ericsson offloading framework to better explore the WebAssembly properties;
 - 2) evolve the offloading framework to support 3D object detection tasks; and
 - 3) design an orchestration solution for WebAssembly modules. Toward supporting 3D object detection in the offloading framework, we opted to work with Cube R-CNN, an extension of Region-based Convolutional Neural Networks (R-CNNs) designed for 3D object detection and pose estimation. As a result of this activity, a demo was accepted in IEEE NOMS 2025 [[RC2.J17](#)].
- **Demonstration of the usability of the CS Dynamic Offloading Framework and the Yollo Object Detection Function.** A simple PoC application can run on a single machine (e.g., the user device) or be offloaded to the edge using the CS Dynamic Offloading Framework.
- The progress obtained with the CS Dynamic Offloading Framework using open technologies such as Rust and C++ was demonstrated internally in Ericsson. The Yollo demo running 2D object detection was showcased as a proof-of-concept.
- **Integration of the CS Dynamic Offloading Framework with the mobile network using EDGEAPP 3GPP specification.** This work is being divided into two parts: UE (developed by this WP) and the Core Network (developed by Ericsson internally). To achieve this goal, Gustavo Jardim, MSc student, started studying EDGEAPP 3GPP specification.
- Another proof-of-concept was demonstrated showing part of the integration of the CS Dynamic Offloading Framework with the 3GPP edge standards, where the AKMA-related functionalities in the User Equipment, leveraging tools, such as PacketRusher and Free5GC Compose were showcased.
- **Configuration of a cluster with k8s in docker (kind) and kasm-operator to run wasm applications.** Also, we started to run WASM workloads natively on the Kubernetes node (without container). This brings faster startup and lower memory usage and is ideal for edge & serverless.
- An empirical evaluation was done comparing WebAssembly offloading for AR. The results were published in SBRC 2024 [[RC2.D16](#)].
- Submission of a journal paper to IEEE Communications Magazine is planned for Q2 2025.

DC3: End-to-end slicing in latency-sensitive networks

The goal of this WP is to deploy and evaluate resource allocation mechanisms that provide delay guarantees for latency-sensitive applications in heterogeneous networks. It is also a target in this WP to start investigating the O-RAN features, trying to map the 3GPP architecture into a closed-control loop to monitor, analyze, and actuate in 5G networks. Federated Learning will be a key part of the closed loop. The solution under investigation will be based on the network slicing paradigm, jointly considering various network aspects, such as multiple slices, routing paths, transmission capacities, applications with diverse requirements, and numerous UEs. By relying on queueing modeling frameworks to map and optimize resource allocation to each network node and network slice instance, guarantees of no delay should be provided. Joint publication drafts have already been worked out and will be submitted soon.

This WP is working on three main aspects:

1. **Fuzzy Agent Deployment and Network Expansion:** the Fuzzy agent was successfully deployed on a Tofino switch, confirming that the results observed in simulations are consistent with real hardware. The Fuzzy agent was further optimized, reducing the decision-making

time from 100 ms to just 1 ms - an exceptional achievement that enhances its suitability for real-world applications;

2. **Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy System (ANFIS) Enhancement:** we are enhancing the Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) to dynamically adjust the parameters of the Gaussian membership functions. This means that each agent deployed on a Tofino switch will incorporate a learning process based on the backpropagation algorithm, optimizing the mean and standard deviation of each membership function to achieve better scheduling performance;
3. **Reinforcement Learning Agent for Comparison:** since we found no directly comparable works in the literature, we are developing a Reinforcement Learning (RL) agent to dynamically adjust the Weighted Round Robin (WRR) algorithm weights. The reward function is based on buffer occupancy, while the penalty function is determined by violations of a predefined buffer threshold.

The main activities and achievements in this period can be summarized as follows:

- **Design and development of a programmable testbed** (using Tofino switches) to serve as the transport network for an O-RAN setup. Working on the control loop using UFSCar's Tofino Switches. This task focuses on reading the queue occupancy of the Tofino switches (uplink) and adjusting the WRR scheduler weights for the Tofino queues (downlink) based on the Fuzzy agent's decisions.
- **Initial experiments with the NVIDIA BlueField-2 DPU and the DOCA framework.** The setup involves a host and the DPU, which are remotely accessed and located at a partner university (UNIPAMPA). Currently, we are replicating a Hairpin application using the DOCA Flow library for traffic routing.
- **Exploring how to leverage rApps, deployed within the Non-RT RIC inside the SMO,** to enable a multi-domain federated learning framework. This approach would not only involve the transport network domain but also integrate the RAN domains, facilitating decisions related to areas such as hardware acceleration for 5G VNFs.
- **Preparation of demo submission** to the SIGCOMM'25 to showcase the capability of our closed-control loop to monitor, analyze, and actuate in 5G networks, specifically configuring the queue weights of two slices deployed in the transport network.
- **Hiring of a Post-doc researcher** to work on leveraging AI/ML for adaptive resource management in Open RAN Architecture. The researcher will start in June 2025.

■ NEWTON - iN Edge netWork indusTrial automation

NW1: Dataplane HW acceleration/offloading of infra/app functions

Offloading strategies to dataplane technologies have gained increasing attention of the networking and cloud communities leveraging advances in programmable HW technologies at the end-host (e.g. SmartNICs) and inside the HW network (e.g. ToP-of-Rack switches). To achieve low latency in scenarios such as industrial automation, several technologies have emerged [Cozzolino et al. 2023] and have been embraced by this WP. The vibrant landscape is composed of SmartNIC / Data Processing Units, eBPF acceleration together with dataplane programmability (e.g. P4/Tofino) [P4, 2024] and In-band Network Telemetry (INT) [INT, 2024].

This WP tackled the challenge of dealing with varying heterogeneous dataplane programmable options (HW & SW) to make the right choice on what and how to accelerate certain functions on virtualized, programmable infrastructures.

After its two-year duration, NW1 comes to its natural end as initially planned but will have continuity in terms of team members and research scope around network programmability in the new NW4, as described later in Section IV on the activity plan for the next period.

The main activities and achievements in Y2 of NW1 can be summarized as follows:

- **In-network QoE Management** method for VR applications directly in the dataplane experimentally evaluated in our hardware-based multiple pipeline network emulator P7. Inter-packet gap metrics are analyzed to estimate the QoE of the VR session. QoE optimization is achieved through queue / priority in the P4 pipeline. The main publication, "Video Streaming QoE Meets Programmable Data Planes: In-Network QoE Management," was published in the IEEE Network journal. [[RC2.A2](#)]
- **Offloading of Robotic and UAV Control** to the network using P4 programmable data planes resulted in one publication, "Harnessing P4 for In-Network Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Collision Avoidance" [[RC2.J10](#)], accepted in IEEE NetSoft 2025. This research thread was part of the PhD work that in previous projects in collaboration with Ericsson [Cesen et al., 2020] and that ultimately was defended within the period and WP scope of SMARTNESS.
- **Data Plane Offloading of Virtual Infrastructure Functions:** Cloud-native applications, characterized by their scalability, resilience, and flexibility, adopt microservices architecture to decompose applications into smaller, independently manageable services. This study identifies the performance bottlenecks arising from the extensive use of service meshes, highlighting the critical issue of CPU overload due to networking-related tasks. The main results were published in IEEE CloudNet "eZtunnel: Leveraging eBPF to Transparently Offload Service Mesh Data Plane Networking" [[RC2.C6](#)] and will be presented in IEEE NetSoft 2025 "eSeMeshA: eBPF-based Service Mesh Acceleration for Cloud-Native Infrastructures" [[RC2J09](#)].
- **Hardware Acceleration and Network Offloading of Security Functions** have been explored by two MSc students: one completed in Y1 together with DisCoNet RS and another [[RC2.H3](#)] in Y2 led by the STA TRU leader, Prof. Marco Amaral. The research results include the P4 implementation and evaluation of the Forro14 stream cipher on Tofino programmable HW [[RC2.D12](#)] and an experimental comparison of the stream ciphers ChaCha, Forro, and Xote [[RC2.J13](#)]. The Invention Disclosure related to kTLS offloading resulted in the filing of patent PCT/EP2025/056322 "COMMUNICATION HANDLING" [[RC2.E1](#)].
- **SmartNIC Programmability & Offloading.** State-of-the art survey on the SmartNIC ecosystem entitled resulted in two tutorials entitled "SmartNICs: The Next Leap in Networking": one international at IEEE NetSoft'24 and one short course at SBRC 2024 published as a book chapter [[RC2.F1](#)]. This work was done in collaboration with the team of DC1, one researcher from RNP and two associated researchers from UFRGS with experience on P4/SmartNICs. This activity contributed to the SMARTNESS hour to share with all participants knowledge about the SmartNIC technologies, ideas on infrastructure sharing across institutions, and support to the purchasing decisions of SmartNICs in 2025. In terms of experimental research, the main achievements are related to investigating the performance and power efficiency of NVIDIA BlueField-2 SmartNICs for in-network resource scaling of VNFs [[RC2.C12](#)].
- **In-network Traffic Classification. Design and implementation of** traffic classification methods entirely done within P4 dataplanes to forward/balance/queue traffic based on the traffic features. The target use cases are related to two latency-sensitive and QoE demanding applications, namely XR/AR and cloud gaming. The main results include open-source software implementations available in SMARTNESS GitHub repositories along with relevant datasets. The results and achievements around traffic classification of cloud gaming and XR/AR using ML models are described in two IEEE NetSoft 2024 publications: "From Pixels to Packets: Traffic Classification of Augmented Reality and Cloud Gaming" [[RC2.C7](#)] and "MATADOR: ML-based Cloud Gaming Traffic Detection Entirely in Programmable Hardware" [[RC2.C16](#)].

- **Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN).** Integrating TSN and wireless networks, like 5G, affords deterministic communication with great flexibility and mobility, enabling new services to be used in smart industries. This activity has provided advances in simulating this integration, using the OMNeT++ open source tool and developing extended modules to support time synchronization between the TSN and 5G based on 3GPP Release 17, which no simulator has fully covered yet: “Towards TSN-5G integration: simulating time synchronization through 5G via OMNeT++” [RC2.D15] and “Bridging TSN and 5G: Synchronization and Flow Mapping for Smart Manufacturing” [RC2.J04].
- **Programmable Network Emulation and Traffic Generation Toolbox.** Impactful and meaningful research towards 6G requires high-fidelity experimental evaluation of existing and new protocols at hardware line-rates and ultra-low-latency high speed. To this end, the WP has devoted large efforts into the required research and development of adequate traffic generation and emulation tools based on P4 programmable Tofino hardware:
 - **PIPO-TG:** Parameterizable high-performance traffic generator, published at IEEE NOMS'24 [RC2.C2];
 - **P4 Replay (P4R):** P4 hardware-based 100Gbps reproduction of packet traces and stateful connections, demonstrated in ACM SIGCOMM'24 [RC2.C10];
 - **TFTG:** Time Fidelity Traffic Generation through P4/Tofino Programmable Hardware, published in the IEEE Network journal [RC2.A3], featuring Time-Sensitive Networking Traffic Generation demonstrated in SBRC'24 [RC2.D14];
 - **P7 emulation** P4/Tofino platform [Rodriguez et al. 2022] is being maintained in our open source repository and being used within the Center and in collaboration with other research groups, resulting in joint publications (e.g. “PINT-BoX: Path-aware networking IN a Tofino BoX” [RC2.C11];
 - All documentation is open source and has been offered as a tutorial at IEEE NFV-SDN 2024: “Recapping Your Programmable Infrastructures in Support of 6G Research: From Network Emulation to Traffic Generation,” <https://github.com/smartness2030/NFV-SDN-P7-PIPOTG-TUTORIAL>

Other noteworthy aspects or future work activities include:

- **One patent filed:** PCT/EP2025/056322 "COMMUNICATION HANDLING" [RC2.E1].
- **Workforce development:**
 - Two PhD thesis defended: “Advanced Data Plane Techniques for 5G: Hardware-Accelerated Hybrid User Plane Functions and Intelligent Traffic Identification and Prioritization” [RC2.I1], “Low-latency in-network applications through programmable data planes” [RC2.I2].²
 - Three MSc dissertations were defended: “Simulation of time synchronization and QoS mapping for TSN-5G integration” [RC2.H1], “eZtunnel: An eBPF-based Traffic Acceleration Mechanism for Cloud-Native Infrastructures” [RC2.H2], and “Design, implementação e avaliação de atestação remota distribuída em plano de dados programável” [RC2.H3].
- **Keynotes** delivered from the core research of NW1 on programmable testbed infrastructures:
 - “*Software Defined Inception: Turning P4/Tofino Programmable Hardware into an Emulation and Traffic Generation Toolbox for Network Slicing Research.*” IEEE NFV-SDN MOBISLICE Workshop, Nov., 2024.
 - “*Software Defined Inception: When your Programmable Network Turns into your Emulation and Traffic Generation Toolbox Towards 6G*”, LANC, Aug. 2024.
- **Exploratory research** on future-looking / complementary topics like Digital Twin Network provisioning [RC2.C8] and P4-based Fast-Rerouting [RC2.C20] presented in IEEE NetSoft'24 ,

² The work of each PhD was initiated prior to the official start of SMARTNESS but followed work plans present in the submission of the ERC proposal and executed during the period.

and “Rethinking the In-band Network Telemetry through Application and Server-Level Network Telemetry” [RC2.C13] presented in the CoNEXT student workshop.

NW2: Internet of Robotic Things (IoRT)

Unlike other WPs emphasizing network and cloud computing enablers for applications such as cloud gaming and XR, this WP focuses on connected robotic systems, known as the Internet of Robotic Things (IoRT). The IoRT aims to enable more intelligent, collaborative, heterogeneous, efficient, self-adaptive, context-aware, and cost-effective robotic networks. Originally centered on building an integrated ecosystem of smart devices and agents in intelligent environments, the research has now shifted to addressing challenges in industrial applications. By converging interdependent technologies, the IoRT presents significant research challenges in integrating robotics, IoT, and cloud computing. Beyond identifying requirements in computing and networking, the primary research questions in this WP have transitioned from social applications, such as healthcare and elderly inclusion, to a stronger focus on industrial use cases.

The main research objectives and achievements of this WP during this period include:

- **IoRT Infrastructure Development:** progress was made in the development of a scalable IoRT architecture using a bottom-up approach based on [RC2.D1] adapted to a more industrial environment. A RESTful communication-based prototype was implemented to demonstrate the memory structure. Additionally, initial integration with Home Assistant (HASS) was carried out to enhance interoperability between IoT devices. Efforts were also directed toward the standardization of communication protocols between IoT devices, Smart Hubs, and central servers. Furthermore, a Telegram-based user interface was developed to enable system supervision and direct interaction.
- **Task Planning in Multi-Agent Systems:** research was conducted on semantic inference and natural language processing (NLP) to improve human-agent interaction. Efforts were also focused on cooperative multi-agent systems, integrating social robots and IoT devices to enhance coordination and functionality in [RC2.D4]. Investigations were carried out on the application of Large Language Models (LLMs) for task planning and robot control. Additionally, distributed architectures were developed to enable interoperability between heterogeneous multi-agent systems. Optimization techniques were explored to improve resource management in LLM-powered multi-agent systems. Task decomposition strategies were analyzed to enhance sequential reasoning and decision-making in dynamic environments. Lastly, experimentation with LangChain was performed to develop episodic memory in multi-agent frameworks.
- **Multi-Agent Dynamic 3D Open-Vocabulary SLAM and Scene Understanding:** Open-vocabulary semantic information was incorporated into multi-agent robotic localization to enhance scene understanding. A review of state-of-the-art, including ConceptGraphs and HOVSG, was conducted to assess their applicability. Further analysis focused on Khronos for spatio-temporal metric-semantic SLAM in dynamic environments. Methodologies were developed to enable real-time execution in multi-agent SLAM applications, addressing computational efficiency and scalability. Challenges related to multi-sensor integration in heterogeneous agent networks were studied to improve data fusion techniques. Additionally, a workflow was created to evaluate RGB-D image processing for SLAM applications, contributing to more robust perception and mapping capabilities to be included in [RC2.D3].
- **Development of the Humanoid Agent SAM:** We had some significant advances on the design and construction of a humanoid agent inspired by Aldebaran’s Pepper robot. A 3D CAD model was developed, incorporating realistic dimensions, kinematics, and dynamics to ensure proper functionality and design accuracy. Initial integration of gesture and facial expression recognition of [RC2.D5] was performed to facilitate non-verbal communication, enhancing the

humanoid agent's interaction capabilities. Additionally, behavior libraries were developed using Aldebaran's Choregraphe software to enable more dynamic and adaptive responses. Movement execution was successfully implemented through Dynamixel motors, allowing the humanoid agent SAM to perform a range of precise actions. The development of the exoskeleton [RC2.D2] under this research grant has been discontinued due to a shift in the target application. Initially designed for a smart home environment to assist the elderly and people with disabilities, the project now focuses on an industrial setting, where research and development of assistive devices like the exoskeleton are no longer a priority.

- **Experimental Validation and Proof of Concept:** Simulation and prototyping efforts were carried out using, at first, the robotic simulation framework CoppeliaSim to test and refine the system. The middleware was developed to manage agent actions, supporting semantic navigation and robotic interaction to ensure seamless communication between agents. In the second phase, initial experimental results were obtained, validating the feasibility of the proposed architectures and task execution frameworks and demonstrating the potential for successful real-world application of the developed systems. A simple setup based on [RC2.D4] was built where human, robotic, and IoT agents interact under the supervision of the smart environment. Human agents are able to ask for some activities to be done by voice or using their mobile phone, and the smart environment makes use of the available resources and capabilities of the agents to attend to the human demand.

■ C3LA - Cognitive Close Control Loops Architecture for Edge IoT

CL1: Mobile Multimedia QoE Estimation

This WP focuses on addressing several key questions for QoE evaluation and analysis of multimedia and Web services in mobile networks. Mobile traffic is expected to keep growing and become the main contributor of overall IP traffic in 2024+.³ Diverse mobile applications such as news, social media, and online shopping lead this shift. Mobile applications have become an integral part of daily life. Users rely on these platforms for communication, entertainment, and information consumption. These applications often operate in various network conditions while interacting with background services like email synchronization, cloud backups, and music streaming. Recent research on traffic modeling primarily focuses on Web-based applications [Luglio et al., 2023], examining user behavior during browsing sessions. However, mobile applications, while built on web technologies, offer different user experiences, performance characteristics, and reliance on multimedia and embedded services. This WP addresses open challenges in the literature regarding the modeling of key mobile apps for generating realistic traffic, considering user interactivity, dynamism, and perceived QoE.

The WP main activities and achievements in this period can be summarized as follows:

- Design and implementation of DCTPQ, an ML-based edge solution that dynamically identifies and prioritizes CG traffic on-the-fly [RC2.J15].
- Deployment of the DCTPQ in the dataplane. As such, the classifier marks AR and CG traffic with Explicit Congestion Notification (ECN) codepoints to integrate with the Low Latency, Low Loss, Scalable Throughput (L4S) features of the programmable switch [RC2.J11].
- Design and implementation of MATADOR, a machine learning system that classifies CG traffic entirely in P4 programmable hardware [RC2.C16].
- Design and implementation of POSMAC, a platform designed to deploy Decision Tree (DT) and Random Forest (RF) models on the NVIDIA DOCA DPU, equipped with an ARM processor, for real-time network traffic classification [RC2.C19].

³ <https://www.ericsson.com/en/reports-and-papers/mobility-report>

- Design and implementation of a mobile traffic generator: The tool simulates mobile Web user application user behaviors under different network conditions. This enables analysis of how network performance impacts mobile application responsiveness, load times, and reliability – all critical components of QoE. By correlating network metrics with calculated QoE, operators can prioritize enhancements for optimal user satisfaction [RC2.C18].
- Developing a mechanism for synthetic network traffic generation using Generative AI by using state-of-the-art approaches such as GANs and Diffusion Models. These research activities resulted in two tutorial offerings: one delivered in IEEE NetSoft 2024, and another as a short course at SBRC 2024 and a book chapter publication, “Generation of Synthetic Datasets in the Context of Computer Networks using Generative Adversarial Networks” [RC2.F3]. These results were achieved in collaboration with DC1 work within the DisCoNet RS.
- Development of new methods for synthetic trace generation (e.g. pcap files) moving beyond the current state-of-the-art such as Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) and Diffusion Models.
- Design and analysis of Data Augmentation techniques using synthetic network-level flow traces for ML-based traffic identification.
- Understanding of YouTube QoE performance in 5G networks and development and evaluation of novel methods for QoE benchmarking and ML-based stall prediction of YouTube over 5G under varying networking and mobility scenarios. The resulting IEEE WCNC publication [RC2.C4] was done in collaboration with researchers from INRIA, France. Results from follow-up investigations have revealed the impact of channel metrics in 5G NSA and SA on video streaming QoE [RC2.J06].
- Public release of all datasets related to 5G performance and YouTube QoE metrics.

Other noteworthy aspects or future work activities include:

- Two PhD BEPE exchanges starting in Q2/25: One at KTH, Sweden, to develop research outlined in [RC2.C21] “Innovative Approaches for Network Analysis and Optimization: Leveraging Deep Learning and Programmable Hardware, and another at AAT, Austria, to work on “QoE Evaluation for Emerging Media Applications: Network-Level Analysis and Traffic Modeling” [RC2.C18].
- Fostering open research: For researchers studying network behavior, realistic datasets and mobile traffic generators are valuable assets for their studies, facilitating the simulation of various workloads and network conditions to analyze the impact on application QoE.

After its two-year duration, CL1 ends as initially planned but will have continuity in terms of some team members and research scope around QoE in CL3 on Immersive Media, as described later in Section IV on the activity plan for the next period.

CL2: Holographic-Type Communications (HTC)

Under the evolving vision of the Internet of Vehicles (IoV), the convergence of Autonomous Vehicles (AVs) and immersive media consumption results in a “Moving Metaverse” that unlocks new possibilities of in-car entertainment through novel opportunities for VR content and gaming during travel. A recent survey [Anwar et al., 2024] describes existing research gaps related to Quality of Experience assessment methodologies for immersive (AR/VR) content consumption in the IoV. Unlike existing AR and VR solutions, holographic services operate in a true three-dimensional media space and leverage multiple senses (i.e., sight, hearing, and touch) to provide truly immersive and exploration experiences, a vision that has been touted as the “Internet of Senses”.⁴

Holograms are expected to be present in our daily routine, including remote presentations, near-real presence education services, military operations, industry digital transformation, tourism, marketing,

⁴ <https://www.ericsson.com/en/6g/internet-of-senses>

entertainment, and others [Clemm et al., 2020]. In this context, holographic-aware cameras and displays will transmit and receive a huge amount of data with ultra-low latency, while interacting with avatars in hologram-based environments. It is expected that holographic-type communications will require Tbps data rates and end-to-end latencies below 1 ms [Akyildiz and Guo, 2022]. The extreme high throughput and latency requirements of holographic avatars cannot be assured by 5G networks and will require changes in 6G wireless systems [Giordani et al., 2020] along with STA advances in networking and computing architectures.

The WP main activities and achievements in this period can be summarized as follows:

- State-of-the-art review of holographic media, from encoding to transport protocol advances (e.g. QUIC-HTTP/3) enabling technologies, and networking / computing requirements of HTC;
- Development of an experimental environment as an enabler of HTC research resulting in a P7-based programmable network testbed to showcase the impact of network QoS on holographic streaming QoE, demonstrated in IEEE NFV-SDN 2024 [RC2.C17];
- Comparative study of QoE in volumetric video transmission in point cloud format rendered on a real Head Mounted Display (HMD) device (Meta Quest 3), evaluating TCP-HTTP and WebRTC protocols for varying network conditions [RC2.J14].
- Research on network slicing, edge computing and candidate in-network functions to improve QoS/QoE of HTC services;
- Development of Meta Quest 3 VR application representing and a digital showroom of the SMARTNESS ERC to feature research activities within WPs, scientific publications, etc. The VR showroom has been used in the demo booths of scientific events (e.g. SBRC'24, NetSoft'24, NFV-SDN'24) and is readily available to visitors of the SMARTNESS laboratory at LCA/FEEC in Unicamp: <https://github.com/smartness2030/SmartnessShowroom>

As a result of the noteworthy results achieved and the increasing research and standardization opportunities in the domain of immersive media, research work will be continued in a new, dedicated WP (CL3) that will incorporate further competencies on XR developed in other SMARTNES WPs.

■ DEMIST - Distributed Edge Computing Swarm Intelligence

DM1: Video delivery at the edge with support for VR/AR

Delivering seamless and high-quality XR experiences demands significant computational power, networking capabilities, and storage resources. Consequently, the associated high computing costs can restrict the range of viable XR experiences on mobile devices with limited resources [Heo, Bhardwaj and Gavrilovska, 2023]. To address these challenges, Fog/Edge computing technologies come into play, aiming to bring Cloud-like features such as resource elasticity and virtualization closer to the end-user [Bittencourt et al., 2017].

This WP was scheduled to end in 2024, and we are currently phasing out its activities with a PhD defense (Eduardo Gama) scheduled for April 30, 2025.

The research objectives and expected results of this WP include:

- Video delivery architectures that respond to XR/AR requirements considering the dynamics of mobile users.
- QoE adaptation for XR applications: developing algorithms and technologies that optimize various aspects of XR, such as reducing latency, enhancing graphics rendering, or improving spatial audio.
- Resource allocation modeling and optimization at the edge for XR/AR applications.

The WP main activities and achievements in this period can be summarized as follows:

- Development of a preliminary XR/AR performance analysis considering how video quality impacts latencies in interactive video content. This analysis was supported by inputs from Mattias Wildeman and Björn Skubic, from Ericsson Research Stockholm. Results suggest QoE adaptation can be considered to include user context so the quality of object detection, quality of video, and response time can be tailored to the specific user application/context in real time.
- Analysis of scenarios where trade-offs between computing capacity and network quality in the edge-cloud continuum interfere in object detection and quality of experience from the user perspective. An illustrative scenario was designed, and preliminary results were obtained that considered mobility in cities (assistive functions for cyclists in cities).
- Evolution of the on-demand video delivery architecture to incorporate QoE aspects related to AR applications.
- Evolution of the AR Application Pipeline Communication to incorporate time-sensitive constraints, enabling more effective decision-making for offloading processing tasks to edge nodes. The video delivery architecture addresses time-sensitive constraints critical for AR applications.
- An updated literature review for video delivery services was conducted in collaboration with Prof. Natesha B. V. from IIIT Raichur, India. A review article is being prepared, in cooperation with Andrew Williams from Ericsson Research, for submission to a journal.
- Development of a content steering mechanism enabling dynamic service selection for video delivery in the computing continuum [\[RC2.C3\]](#).
- Presentation of a demo entitled "Exploring the Content Steering Server for Adaptive Video Streaming in the Edge-Cloud Continuum" at Ericsson Research Day in Brazil in Sep. 2024.
- Presentation of a short course titled "Content Steering: Leveraging the Computing Continuum to Support Adaptive Video Streaming", presented at the Brazilian Symposium on Computer Networks and Distributed Systems in 2024, published as a book chapter [\[RC2.F2\]](#).
- Funded by CISB, Luiz Bittencourt gave a talk to Prof. Fredrik Heintz at Linköping University on Sept. 13, covering aspects of WP1.
- Design and implementation of mechanisms to support the use of Machine Learning in the decision-making process for video delivery services. The aim is to predict the Quality of Experience according to the behavior of users in order to proactively deploy video services/caching on the edge of the network.
- Interactions with Klaus Raizer and Amadeu Nascimento from Ericsson Research Brazil to support them in using the containerized platform developed in this WP, in other reinforcement learning setups.
- Preparation and presentation titled "Enabling Adaptive Video Streaming on the Edge-Cloud Network" during a meeting with Prof. Fredrik Heintz on November 14, 2024, at the Instituto de Computação, Unicamp.
- Eduardo Gama has worked on his thesis finalization and writing, whose defense is scheduled for April 30, 2025. The thesis title is "An Architecture for Adaptive Video Streaming: QoE Forecasting, Content Steering, and Scalable Resource Management through Edge-Cloud Computing".
- Fundamental service computing distribution concepts and management have been under investigation in cooperation with Prof. Roberto Filho, from UFSC, towards a self-distributed platform. A paper on these fundamental aspects has been accepted for publication [\[RC2J08\]](#).
- Design and implementation of a multi-armed bandits approach for stateful services allocation in self-distributed systems [\[RC2.C5\]](#).
- Design and incorporation of Reinforcement Learning based decision-making in content steering scenarios considering AR/VR requirements and applications.

Other noteworthy aspects or future work activities to be developed in this research topic include:

- An adaptive offloading controller for XR applications to control performance and offloading decision-making in the device-edge-cloud landscape for 6G scenarios.
- Adaptive offloading decision-making based on network conditions, available computing power, video quality adaptation, and user context.

DM2: Edge-assisted intelligent drone management

A smart aerial delivery service uses drones to deliver packages in urban areas, replacing or supplementing terrestrial vehicles. Intelligent drone delivery is vital in reducing the environmental impact, delivery time, and costs, calling the attention of delivery companies that started to perform small-scale tests with drones and providers offering this service, such as Alphabet's Wing. In big cities, a drone delivery service will employ many drones, increasing drone density and bringing the fundamental challenge of avoiding collisions with other drones or typical obstacles of urban spaces. Drones fly at low altitudes, increasing the probability of collision with buildings, trees, mountains, birds, or even other drones [Al-Mousa et al., 2019]. In a scenario with a high density of obstacles, drones may need a set of collision avoidance strategies to apply the most appropriate technique in each situation [Yasin et al., 2020].

The research objectives and expected results of this WP include:

- Develop collision-avoidance mechanisms for scenarios where a high density of drones is expected.
- Design an architecture to support drone management using edge/fog computing associated with 6G communication infrastructures.
- Architect and implement distributed machine learning mechanisms in the edge, enabling edge intelligence for drone management systems.

The WP main activities and achievements in this period can be summarized as follows:

- Team expansion to incorporate one principal investigator from FEEC/Unicamp (Prof. Fernando Von Zuben) and one associate researcher from UFPI (Prof. Francisco Airton Silva), as well as new PhD and MSc students.
- Modeling of optimization problems that aggregate trucks to support drone delivery services, where trucks can act as mobile drone pads and charging stations, namely dealing with the truck-drone routing problem (TDRP) as a bilevel and multi-objective optimization in a 6G assisted environment.
- A comparative analysis of studies from the literature was conducted, focusing on identifying approaches to multi-drone path planning focusing on Reinforcement Learning and Metaheuristics for Dynamic and Combinatorial Optimization.
- Analysis of the impact of communication delays when processing anti-collision decision-making algorithms at the network edge with different communication technologies [RC2.D8].
- Development of a reinforcement learning approach for collision avoidance and execution of experiments to compare to geometric approaches from the literature, showing superior performance.
- Developed a literature review on Computational Approaches to Collision Prevention in Drone Delivery in cooperation with Prof. Francisco Airton Silva, Leonel Feitosa Correia, and Vandirleya Barbosa from UFPI.
- Also, in cooperation with UFPI, we performed the modeling of various drone collision scenarios analytically using stochastic petri nets [RC2.J19].

- Initial modeling of and results of using edge computing to manage drones [RC2.D7], and extended analysis and experiments resulting in the paper “Edge4Drone: Managing Landings and Takeoffs in High-Density Distribution Centers” accepted in the NetRobics Workshop to be held at IEEE INFOCOM 2025 [RC2.J12].
- Novel simulation tools and frameworks. In support of the WP activities related to different evaluation needs, complementary simulation frameworks based on open-source projects are being developed and have proved very useful for the research objectives.
 - Several improvements in the UTSim simulator functionalities for collision avoidance and edge management also resulted in the refactoring of the UTSim simulator core to be more readable and with proper documentation.
 - Investigations on improving drone simulations: how accelerating the simulation impacts the simulation steps to understand the limits of scalability versus precision when simulating drone scenarios and the execution of scalability experiments with up to ~400 drones/min to assess the behavior of a Reinforcement Learning approach developed for the collision avoidance problem.
 - Design and implementation of the UNetyEmu framework, combining Unity and Mininet-WiFi, enabling realistic multi-vehicle experiments with both aerial and ground mobility alongside network emulation.
 - Simulation-based analysis of urban air traffic and logistics in future Smart cities applications, 5G vehicular communication, edge computing for different UAV/ground mobility and network performance scenarios.
 - The Unity-based simulator for aerial and non-aerial vehicles with integrated network emulation (UNetyEmu) [RC2.J05] was submitted as a demo to SBRC along with all necessary documentation and code released in the open source repository <https://github.com/smartness2030/UNetyEmu>.
 - Implementation of battery-draining models into the simulation tools used by the group.

Other noteworthy actions or future work perspectives include:

- Funded by CISB, Luiz Bittencourt participated in the WARA.PS demonstration week and visited Saab in Linköping, Sweden, on Sept. 15, interacting with several Saab researchers and with Fredrik Gunnarsson from Ericsson Research.
- Funded by CISB, Luiz Bittencourt gave a talk to Prof. Fredrik Heintz group at Linköping University on Sept. 13, covering aspects of WP2 and igniting immediate collaboration with Amath Sow, a PhD student from Fredrik's group interested in using our simulation frameworks.
- Strengthening the collaboration with Prof. Fredrik Heintz (LiU) and PhD student Amath Sow from Linköping University, Sweden. The technical cooperation in modeling drone simulation and path planning along with collision avoidance is advancing, and future perspectives include further technical visits and student exchange during Y3 (e.g. PhD Mauricio Rodriguez has started to plan a work plan for a BEPE scholarship to LiU).

■ ADVENTURE - Adaptive and Secure Network Applications over Industrial Internet

WP1: Network Software Testing

The softwarization of computer networks requires continuous testing of all the logic components running both at the network's core and edge. This WP continued to have advances in applying fuzzing testing to evaluate the implementation of network protocols. Two different protocols were the focus of last year: the Security Protocol Data Model (SPDM) and the Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP). SPDM is relevant in the context of SMARTNESS because it can be used to guarantee

hardware security [DMTF 2023b]. For instance, with SPDM, a commodity server can have guarantees that it was not maliciously modified since it was moved from the retailer to the telecom company before being used to instantiate Virtual Network Functions. AMQP is relevant in the context of SMARTNESS due to its low latency, which is very important in 5G and B5G applications.

The WP main activities and achievements in this period can be summarized as follows:

- Development of SPDM-WiD, a dissector for the SPDM protocol in the wireshark sniffer to facilitate debugging the fuzzer to be developed [RC2.D13].
- Final results of the application of a fuzzer to test SPDM implementations [RC2.D11].
- The preliminary version of a grammar-based fuzzer to test AMQP brokers.

Further noteworthy aspects or future work activities include:

- Sharing of three software systems as free and open source software: the SPDM-WiD⁵, the SPDM fuzzer⁶, and the AMQP fuzzer (this last one still private).
- Publishing of a video describing how to install and use the SPDM-WiD⁷.
- Possibility of using tools based on Artificial Intelligence, such as LLMs, to accelerate the construction of the fuzzer for the SPDM protocol.

The activities of this WP related to the SPDM protocol were carried on by the undergrad student Thiago Duvanel Ferreira who received a scientific initiation scholarship linked to the project (not BCO) from January 2024 until September 2024. Activities related to the AMQP protocol are being carried on by the undergrad student Ivan Gabriel Ferreira Dias, without a scholarship from the project. This WP is finished, and future works will be inserted in the new WP about Distributed Intelligence for Secure 6G Network Services, using BCOs for the students now that the RS leader has been promoted to PI.

WP2: Differentiation and Prioritization of Smart Grid Traffic

A smart grid is an architecture for distributing electrical energy integrated with communication technologies used in the Internet. In the SMARTNESS project, it is considered that the mechanisms brought by 5G and B5G networks will meet the requirements of smart grids. In particular, in this research strand, we plan to design an architecture on new mobile network technologies to enable efficient services between the elements of smart grids. Even though some authors already consider that this architecture should be based on network slicing [Li et al. 2020], the various functionalities required for a smart grid to operate justify the need for specific slices for various operations, such as smart metering, distribution automation, inspection based on UAVs and precise load control. Each of these operations needs to be performed using a specific protocol.

To interconnect devices, there is already the IEC61850 standard [International Electrotechnical Commission's (IEC) Technical Committee 57 2023] which in turn defines the GOOSE (Generic Object Oriented System Event), MMS (Manufacturing Message Specification), and SV (Sampled Values) protocols. GOOSE is used for communication between IEDs in a publish-subscribe architecture, SV is used for communication between measurement sensors and IEDs in a unilateral architecture, and MMS is used for communication between IEDs and command centers in a client-server architecture, with the servers running on the IEDs.

The research objectives and expected results of this WP include:

⁵ <https://github.com/th-duvanel/spdm-wid?tab=readme-ov-file>

<https://github.com/th-duvanel/riscv-spdm>

⁶ <https://github.com/th-duvanel/spdmfuzzer/tree/sbseq24>

⁷ <https://youtu.be/Wl6sOXs2tmg>

- To evaluate the impact of using 5G/B5G to transport data from smart grids.
- To introduce new mechanisms that guarantee prioritizing this traffic in specific situations.
- To create a simulation software environment to carry out experiments involving the transport of smart grid traffic in future networks.

The WP main activities and achievements in this period can be summarized as follows:

- Comparison of smart grid simulators.
- Start of development of an ns-3 module to allow smart grid simulations following the protocols specified in the IEC61850 standard.

Additional noteworthy aspects or future work activities include:

- Sharing the ns-3 module as a contribution to the smart grid community.
- Evaluation of realistic smart grid scenarios considering the Brazilian energy system.

The activities of this WP are being carried on by the MSc student Lucas Seiki Oshiro, without a scholarship from the project. This WP is finished, and related future work will be included in the new WP about Distributed Intelligence for Secure 6G Network Services.

WP3: Blockchain-Based Governance Mechanisms

The development of beyond-5G (B5G) and 6G networks requires a transition from traditional network-centric metrics, such as Quality of Service (QoS), to user-centric metrics like Quality of Experience (QoE) [Kougioumtzidis et al. 2022]. This transition is motivated by the expected proliferation of digital applications, including Virtual Reality (VR) and immersive holography, where user experience is a primary concern. Unlike QoS, which captures objective network parameters such as latency and throughput, QoE reflects users' subjective perceptions and satisfaction, containing cognitive and behavioral dimensions. As a result, future 6G systems are expected to emphasize QoE to align with the requirements of these emerging applications [Tondwalkar et al. 2024].

Existing privacy methods offer potential solutions but also present distinct challenges. Federated Learning (FL), considered a candidate approach for future networks [Kazmi et al. 2024], faces limitations regarding communication overhead and security vulnerabilities like data poisoning and inference attacks [Sirohi et al. 2023]. Differential Privacy (DP) can provide mathematical privacy guarantees, but often at the cost of reduced data utility, which exemplifies the broader privacy-QoE trade-off. Furthermore, while encrypted traffic analysis may allow inference of high-level QoE metrics, it contends with computational demands and difficulties arising from evolving encryption protocols and operations on encrypted data.

The research objectives and expected results of this WP include:

- A decentralized architecture that combines blockchain technology with Fast Fully Homomorphic Encryption over the Torus (TFHE).
- A verifiable computation mechanism allows network nodes to verify the correctness of computations in a decentralized manner independently.

The WP main activities and achievements in this period can be summarized as follows:

- A systematic literature review on privacy-preserving QoE techniques [[RC2.J02](#)].
- A TFHE-based QoE architecture and a preliminary proof-of-concept implementation and evaluation [[RC2.J01](#)].

All research outputs of this WP are supported by a public repository containing data and software to ensure reproducibility⁸. The activities of this WP are being carried on by the PhD student Rodrigo Dutra Garcia with a scholarship from the project under the supervision of Co-PI Prof. Jó Ueyama (USP). The activities of this WP will continue next year. The only change is in the numbering (it will be the WP2, now that the previous WP1 and WP2 are joined in the new WP1).

D. Lab Infrastructures

One of the objectives of SMARTNESS is to set up a multi-site testbed based on interconnected experimental facilities deployed at the partner institutions in order to support several application scenarios, as illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6. SMARTNESS testbeds plans and selected technologies for cutting-edge research

Target experiments include (1) drone control and VR experiences managed via a 5G-enabled smartphone, (2) smart grid monitoring via a smart power meter, and (3) demos of vehicular networks with radio-controlled miniature model cars, Raspberry Pi, and Arduino boards. The processing of the data generated by the applications can be done in a computer powered with a GPU (4) emulating the edge of the network. When this processing is not needed, the data produced will be accessed directly from the application scenarios (5). At the top of the figure is presented the main connection and decision infrastructure of the island: P4-compatible switches (6) connected to a server featuring a SmartNIC (7) providing core network emulation capabilities. The existing infrastructure (8) of each institution will also be integrated into each SMARTNESS island via P4 programmable switches.

■ SMARTNESS - LEMAC Facilities

The SMARTNESS main laboratory is currently undergoing renovations to accommodate all the technological infrastructure that will support the center's research and development. The main testbed will be installed in the area of LEMAC - Laboratory of Applied and Computational Electromagnetism at FEEC, featuring a fully anechoic chamber for measurements up to 18GHz, and a VNA for measurements up to 500GHz will be installed in partnership with FAPESP EMU ALTAVE.

The following images show the proposed layout for the new laboratory, as well as the current progress of the renovation works.

⁸ <https://github.com/rodrigodg1/privacy-qoe-system>

be located at FEEC LEMAC and connected to intelligent edge computing facilities and front-line equipment for robotic and computer vision applications.

All equipment for the private 5G network can be hosted in a 19" server rack with at least 5 rack units supporting the following computing and networking hardware required for the testbed which:

- Router (1 RU): Connecting Basebands, Servers and external networks
- Baseband 5G (1 RU) - Interfacing 5G Antennas and the EPC
- Indoor Radio Unit (RU) - Cabled to four indoor antennas and connected to the 5G Baseband
- Server for EPC (1 RU) - Hosting the Evolved Packet Core
- Server for Applications (1 RU) - Hosting on supporting services and applications
- Power 48V DC Supply (2 RU)

Figure 8a. 5G SA Private Network

Figure 8b. 19" server rack.

With indoor 5G SA, our connectivity will be unique for carrying out an experimental evaluation of use cases of the WPs, featuring Proof of Concepts including XR devices, SmartNICs, and servers, altogether enhancing the technological and research capabilities for Y3.

E. Education and Dissemination of Knowledge (EDK)

All the details of the SMARTNESS Education and Dissemination of Knowledge (EDK) year 2 accomplishments are available in the EDK Report #02 (REDK2). In alignment with its focus on educational initiatives and knowledge dissemination, SMARTNESS has structured its efforts in Education and Dissemination of Knowledge (EDK) into different distinct dimensions, namely "Communications," "Scientific Events," "Workforce Development," "Presentations," and "Publications".

This structured approach has notably elevated the visibility of SMARTNESS through the establishment of a cohesive and well-defined visual identity across various dissemination channels. This visual identity has been integrated into diverse media platforms such as the project website, social media channels, newsletters, press releases, interviews, general meetings, and regular update sessions, ensuring consistent and prominent representation. Consequently, this concentrated effort has not only heightened awareness of SMARTNESS within the scientific community but has also cultivated a sense of unity and recognition among stakeholders. Furthermore, SMARTNESS has actively engaged with the scientific community beyond mere awareness-building, fostering active participation and contribution. Through the organization and participation in prominent scientific events such as NOMS, NetSoft, and SBRC, SMARTNESS has significantly advanced knowledge in its respective fields. Additionally, its involvement in talent-building initiatives, including undergraduate research projects, postdoctoral recruitment, and the provision of short courses and tutorials, has strengthened its impact on the scientific landscape.

Looking forward, SMARTNESS expects sustained growth and influence, particularly through initiatives like lab visits and the integration of new educational materials into postgraduate and extension courses. The establishment of a culture focused on high-impact publications, as demonstrated by the substantial number of high-quality publications within the first two years of operation, is also expected to contribute significantly to its future impact.

F. Technology Transfer (TT)

Given the collaborative nature of academia-industry FAPESP ERC, the SMARTNESS ERC has strategically devised multiple technology transfer endeavors aimed at effectively disseminating impactful technical and scientific outcomes to individuals, corporations, and governmental bodies. Central to this strategy in SMARTNESS is the Plan for Technology Transfer (PTT), which is structured around five core pillars: Open Research, Technological Knowledge Transfer, Research spin-offs, Standardization, and Intellectual Property.

In this second year, SMARTNESS continues to demonstrate notable achievements, including the establishment of public software repositories, publication of works concerning open software and data, creation of open data repositories, implementation of internal best practices pertaining to Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), and collaboration with innovation agencies.

For a more in-depth understanding of fundamental concepts and empirical findings, the Technology Transfer Report #02 (RTT2) offers a comprehensive overview of the SMARTNESS Technology Transfer initiative, laying a robust groundwork for further investigation and examination.

G. Management, Structure and Governance Plan (GEO)

A comprehensive and detailed examination of SMARTNESS Management, Structure, and Governance (GEO) initiatives is provided in the GEO yearly Report #02 (RGEO2). This report meticulously outlines essential concepts and empirical evidence, serving to underscore the achievements attained through the implementation of SMARTNESS' GEO action plan, including:

Organization: This encompasses our overarching management structure, featuring an Executive Committee (EC), a Scientific & Technology Advancements Board (STAB) divided into Research Strands (RS) and Scientific & Technology Areas (STA), support from Ericsson Research (ER), and input from the International Advisory Board (IAB).

Quality Assurance and Risk Management: This involves reviewing processes and data management procedures, adhering to FAIR data principles, and practices for risk management.

Communication Tools: This entails the adoption of social network platforms, data repositories, and mailing lists to facilitate effective communication.

Administrative Procedures and Workflows: This includes protocols for news and knowledge dissemination, content publication, evaluation and approval of Work Packages, submission of publications, and scheduling of regular technical and administrative meetings.

Periodic Reports: This pertains to reports addressing management, technical, and financial aspects of SMARTNESS, providing periodic insights into project dimensions.

III. Institutional Support

After the second year of activities, we can report that all the required institutional support is still being provided on various fronts, serving as key support for achieving the Center's objectives efficiently and effectively. Among institutional support actions in Y2, we can highlight:

UNICAMP Research Pro-Rectorate (PRP). The Grant Office (GO) affiliated with UNICAMP's PRP is designed to provide institutional support to researchers by reducing the administrative tasks inherent in conducting research. The GO assists researchers in seeking opportunities —both for research funding and for participation in national and international research groups— in the preparation, submission, execution, and completion of research projects, as well as in disseminating their results, thereby affording them effective, quality time to dedicate to research activities.

Through Resolution CEPE-A-001/2024, on 06/02/2024, the Support Program for the Management of Large Thematic Research Centers⁹ was created, under the coordination of the Dean of Research, which aims to complement the operating infrastructure of large-scale projects. The Program is made up of three support subprograms:

1. **Postdoctoral Scholarship Subprogram in Research Management (PPDG)** aims to meet the needs of large thematic centers with three modalities: Education Management and Knowledge Diffusion (EKD), Technology Transfer and Innovation (TTI) Management, and Executive Project Management (EPM).
2. **Higher Level Technical Support Subprogram (ProATS)** aims to meet the needs of higher education professionals to work and operate equipment installed in large research centers.
3. **Infrastructure Support Subprogram (InfraPeq)** aims to finance the recovery or improvement of existing facilities, as well as adaptations to spaces to meet new demands at two research centers.

The SMARTNESS ERC has received significant support as described next.

- **Completion of the Management team through two new PPDG grants.** Dr. Eduardo Sartori has taken on the role of Technology Transfer Manager, as outlined in the SMARTNESS Technology Transfer (TT) Yearly Report (RTT2). The management team has been further reinforced with the appointment of Dr. Virginia Therezinha Kesting (UNICAMP) as the Education and Knowledge Dissemination (EKD) Manager, as detailed in the SMARTNESS EDK REDK2 document. In Y3, the SMARTNESS ERC has all three management positions supported through UNICAMP PPDG.
- **Lab reform additional support through “InfraPeq.”** The SMARTNESS proposal was awarded R\$ 150,000.00 in January 2025 and is being used for renovation expenses of the new 5G laboratory facilities LEMAC-SMARTNESS located at FEEC/UNICAMP.

Institutional Support Office for Researchers (EAIP - *Escritório de Apoio Institucional ao Pesquisador*, in Portuguese) of the Faculty of Electrical and Computer Engineering (FEEC/UNICAMP): This office, established in 2021, supports faculty members in managing their research projects. SMARTNESS has been adequately supported in all the requested aspects.

UNICAMP Innovation Agency (INOVA): SMARTNESS has sought guidance and improvement on IPR practices through close collaboration with INOVA as described in SMARTNESS Y2 Technology Transfer Yearly Report (RTT2)

UNICAMP Institutional Communication Secretariat (SCI): Provide support in building communication strategies with the internal and external community of FEEC, assisting in the

⁹ <https://prp.unicamp.br/en/grandes-centros/programa-de-apoio/>

dissemination of the faculty's results and safeguarding its visual identity and public relations. SMARTNESS has been using SCI's services and support for communication with society, whether in interaction with the press or in the preparation and dissemination of news.

Provision of physical space at FEEC/UNICAMP for the establishment of the main SMARTNESS laboratory in a 120 m² space, under reform to be equipped with a private 5G network, as detailed in the "Lab Infrastructures / Testbeds" section of this scientific report.

FUNCAMP (UNICAMP Development Foundation) administrative services have provided all the necessary expertise for successful project management support, aiding UNICAMP as the host institution in managing the financial resources and assets contributed by ERICSSON financially.

As reported, UNICAMP has directed significant efforts to support needs related to research management, administration, and physical space of SMARTNESS, mainly due to the evident competence and excellence of its research and development activities.

IV. List of Publications

All publications include their DOI links and are publicly available through the SMARTNESS publications website (<https://smartness2030.tech/publications/>), the Zenodo community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/smartness2030/>

A) Papers in indexed scientific periodicals

- RC2.A1** Marina Martinelli, Luis Antônio Leite Francisco da Costa, Alysso Mazoni, Juliano Luis Pereira Sanches, and Rafael Kunst. **“Strategic Connectivity in 5G and 6G and Remote Surgery: The Case of Germany”**. In Research, Society and Development, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.33448/rsd-v13i7.46402>.
- RC2.A2** Francisco Vogt, Fabricio Rodriguez, Ariel Goes, Suneet Singh, Marcelo Luizelli, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, and Gianni Antichi. **“Video Streaming QoE Meets Programmable Data Planes: In-Network QoE Management.”** In IEEE Network, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/MNET.2024.3509816>.
- RC2.A3** Francisco Germano Vogt, Sergio Rossi Brito da Silva, Fabricio Eduardo Rodriguez Cesen, Filipo Gabert Costa, Marcelo Caggiani Luizelli, and Christian Esteve Rothenberg. **“TFTG: Time Fidelity Traffic Generation through P4/Tofino Programmable Hardware.”** In IEEE Network, 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/MNET.2025.3551515>.

B) Papers in non-indexed scientific periodicals

C) Papers presented at international conferences

- RC2.C1** Felipe A. S. Novais and Fábio L. Verdi, **“Unlocking Security to the Board: An Evaluation of SmartNIC-driven TLS Acceleration with kTLS,”** in IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium (NOMS), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/NOMS59830.2024.10575053>.
- RC2.C2** Filipo Gabert Costa, Francisco Vogt, Fabricio Eduardo Rodriguez Cesen, Ariel Góes de Castro, Marcelo Caggiani Luizelli, and Christian Esteve Rothenberg, **“PIPO-TG: Parameterizable High-Performance Traffic Generation,”** in IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium (NOMS), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/NOMS59830.2024.10575636>.
- RC2.C3** Roberto Rodrigues-Filho, Eduardo S. Gama, Marcio Assis, Roger Immich, Edmundo Madeira, and Luiz F. Bittencourt, **“Content Steering for Adaptive Video Streaming over the Edge-Cloud Continuum,”** in 8th IEEE International Conference on Fog and Edge Computing (ICFEC), 2024.
- RC2.C4** R. U. Mustafa, C. Barakat, and C. E. Rothenberg, **“YouTube goes 5G: QoE Benchmarking and ML-based Stall Prediction,”** in IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/WCNC57260.2024.10571175>.
- RC2.C5** Frederico Meletti Rappa, Roberto Rodrigues-Filho, Alison R. Panisson, Leandro Marcolino, and Luiz F. Bittencourt, **“Multi-armed Bandits for Self-distributing Stateful Services across Networking Infrastructures,”** in IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium (NOMS), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/NOMS59830.2024.10575692>.

- RC2.C6** Arthur J. Simas, Fabricio E. Rodriguez Cesen, and Christian Esteve Rothenberg, **“eZtunnel: Leveraging eBPF to Transparently Offload Service Mesh Data Plane Networking,”** in IEEE International Conference on Cloud Networking (IEEE CloudNet), 2024. DOI: [10.1109/CloudNet62863.2024.10815862](https://doi.org/10.1109/CloudNet62863.2024.10815862)
- RC2.C7** Alireza Shirmarz, Fábio Luciano Verdi, Suneet Kumar Singh, and Christian Esteve Rothenberg, **“From Pixels to Packets: Traffic Classification of Augmented Reality and Cloud Gaming,”** in 10th IEEE International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/NetSoft60951.2024.10588893>.
- RC2.C8** Marcelo Caggiani Luizelli, Francisco Germano Vogt, Paulo Souza, Arthur Francisco Lorenzon, Roberto Irajá Tavares da Costa Filho, **Fábio Diniz Rossi, Rodrigo N. Calheiros, and Christian Esteve Rothenberg,** **“DigiNet: Scaling up Provisioning of Network Digital Twin,”** in 10th IEEE International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/NetSoft60951.2024.10588932>.
- RC2.C9** Diego Medeiros de Abreu, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, and Antônio Jorge Gomes Abelém, **“QML-IDS: Quantum Machine Learning Intrusion Detection System,”** in IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (ISCC), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.ieeecomputersociety.org/10.1109/ISCC61673.2024.10733655>.
- RC2.C10** Francisco Germano Vogt, Fabricio Rodriguez, Filipo Gabert Costa, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, Marcelo Caggiani Luizelli, Gyanesh Patra, and Gergely Pongrácz, **“DEMO: P4 Replay (P4R): Reproducing Packet Traces and Stateful Connections at Line-Rate on Your P4-capable Hardware,”** in ACM SIGCOMM Posters and Demos '24 (SIGCOMM), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3672202.3673743>.
- RC2.C11** Everson S. Borges, Willen B. Coelho, Fabricio R. Cesen, Francisco G. Vogt, Christian Rothenberg, Rodolfo S. Villaça, Cristina K. Dominicini, Rafael S. Guimarães, and Magnos Martinello, **“PINT-BoX: Path-aware networking IN a Tofino BoX,”** in IEEE Conference on Network Function Virtualization and Software Defined Networks (IEEE NFV-SDN), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15178426>
- RC2.C12** Francisco Germano Vogt, Fabricio Rodriguez, Marcelo Caggiani Luizelli, and Christian FEsteve Rothenberg, **“Poster: Towards In-Network Resource Scaling of VNFs,”** in Poster in International Conference On Emerging Networking Experiments And Technologies (CoNEXT), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3680121.3699888>.
- RC2.C13** Francisco Germano Vogt, Fabricio Rodriguez, Marcelo Caggiani Luizelli, and Christian Esteve Rothenberg, **“Rethinking the In-band Network Telemetry: Towards Application and Server-Level Network Telemetry,”** in Student Workshop at International Conference On Emerging Networking Experiments And Technologies (CoNEXT), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3694812.3699922>.
- RC2.C14** Washington R. D. Silva, Fábio L. Verdi, Guilherme M. V. Matos, and Andrew Williams, **“Delivering Augmented Reality to the Edge: An Approach Toward Object Recognition through the In-Network Computing Paradigm,”** in Student Workshop at International Conference On Emerging Networking Experiments And Technologies (CoNEXT), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3694812.3699933>
- RC2.C15** Guilherme Matos, Fabio Verdi, Washington Dias, and Andrew Williams, **“DECOMPOSER: Functional Decomposition of Monolithic Applications to Heterogeneous Resources in Disaggregated Environments,”** in Student Workshop at International Conference On Emerging Networking Experiments And Technologies (CoNEXT), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3694812.3699930>.
- RC2.C16** Suneet Kumar Singh, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, Alireza Shirmarz, Fábio Luciano Verdi, Israat Haque, Gyanesh Patra, and Gergely Pongrácz, **“MATADOR: ML-based**

Cloud Gaming Traffic Detection entirely in Programmable Hardware,” in IEEE Conference on Network Function Virtualization and Software Defined Networks (**IEEE NFV-SDN**), 2024. DOI: [10.1109/NFV-SDN61811.2024.10807465](https://doi.org/10.1109/NFV-SDN61811.2024.10807465)

RC2.C17 Alan Teixeira da Silva, Rafael P. Clerici, Fabricio F. Cesen, Md Tariqul Islam, and Christian E. Rothenberg, **“Programmable Network Testbed for QoS/QoE Assessment of Holographic Media Delivery,”** in IEEE Conference on Network Function Virtualization and Software Defined Networks (**IEEE NFV-SDN**), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14825375>

RC2.C18 Md Tariqul Islam and Christian Esteve Rothenberg, **“QoE Evaluation for Emerging Media Applications: Network-Level Analysis and Traffic Modeling,”** in IEEE Conference on Network Function Virtualization and Software Defined Networks (**IEEE NFV-SDN**), 2024. DOI: [10.1109/NFV-SDN61811.2024.10807495](https://doi.org/10.1109/NFV-SDN61811.2024.10807495).

RC2.C19 Alireza Shirmarz, Fábio Luciano Verdi, Suneet Kumar Singh, and Christian Esteve Rothenberg, **“POSMAC: Powering Up In-Network AR/CG Traffic Classification with Online Learning,”** in IEEE Conference on Network Function Virtualization and Software Defined Networks (**IEEE NFV-SDN**), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14930944>

RC2.C20 Daniel De Lima, Francisco Vogt, Alan Teixeira da Silva, Fabricio Rodriguez Cesen, and Christian Esteve Rothenberg, **“RESISTING: A New Fast-Reroute Mechanism with Packet Distribution on P4-Programmable Switches,”** in IEEE Conference on Network Function Virtualization and Software Defined Networks (**IEEE NFV-SDN**), 2024. DOI: [10.1109/NFV-SDN61811.2024.10807507](https://doi.org/10.1109/NFV-SDN61811.2024.10807507).

RC2.C21 Ariel Góes de Castro and Christian Esteve Rothenberg, **“Innovative Approaches for Network Analysis and Optimization: Leveraging Deep Learning and Programmable Hardware,”** in 10th IEEE International Conference on Network Softwarization (**NetSoft**), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/NetSoft60951.2024.10588944>.

RC2.C22 Christian Esteve Rothenberg. **“Perspectives on 6G in Brazil: A SMARTNESS View”.** In EUCNC 6G Summit CONASENSE Workshop (**EUCNC**), 2024. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15119902](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15119902).

D) Papers presented at Brazilian conferences

RC2.D1 Felipe Augusto Oliveira Mota, César Bastos da Silva, Ervin Alain Bolivar Huayhua, Breno Miranda Portela, and Eric Rohmer. **“IoRT multi-agent for assistive homes: First Test.”** In 10th Congress of the Brazilian Institute of Neuroscience and Neurotechnology (**BRAINN**), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISCC61673.2024.10733655>

RC2.D2 C. M. S. Freitas, V. A. Ferman, and E. Rohmer. **“Robotic lower limb exoskeleton: A control software.”** In 10th Congress of the Brazilian Institute of Neuroscience and Neurotechnology (**BRAINN**), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15047996>

RC2.D3 Ervin Alain Bolivar Huayhua, Eric Rohmer, Felipe Augusto Oliveira Mota, César Bastos da Silva, and Breno Miranda Portela. **“Enhancing Assistive Home Environments through IoRT Multi-Agent Interaction: Model Selection and Robotic Operations.”** In 10th Congress of the Brazilian Institute of Neuroscience and Neurotechnology (**BRAINN**), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15047998>

RC2.D4 César Bastos da Silva, Felipe Augusto Oliveira Mota, Ervin Alain Bolivar Huayhua, Breno Miranda Portela, and Eric Rohmer. **“Robotic Structuring of an Assistive Home: Experimental Test.”** In 10th Congress of the Brazilian Institute of Neuroscience and Neurotechnology (**BRAINN**), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15048000>

- RC2.D5** Breno Portela, César da Silva, Felipe Mota, Ervin Huayhua, and Eric Rohmer. “**Emotive Gestural Expressions for Assistive Home Humanoid Robots: Simulation Test.**” In 10th Congress of the Brazilian Institute of Neuroscience and Neurotechnology (BRAINN), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15048002>
- RC2.D6** Diego Medeiros de Abreu, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, and Antônio Jorge Gomes Abelém. “**qIDS: Sistema de Detecção de Ataques baseado em Aprendizado de Máquina Quântico Híbrido.**” In SBRC 2024 - XLII Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/sbrc.2024.1353>.
- RC2.D7** Lucas de Paula Soares, Fabíola M. C. de Oliveira, Carlos A. Kamienski, and Luiz F. Bittencourt. “**Computação na Borda para Drones: Gerenciando Pousos e Decolagens em Centros de Distribuição.**” In SBRC 2024 - XLII Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/sbrc.2024.1406>.
- RC2.D8** Arthur A. Ferreira, Fabíola M. C. de Oliveira, Luiz F. Bittencourt, and Carlos A. Kamienski. “**O Impacto do Atraso de Comunicação nos Algoritmos Anticolisão de Drones.**” In SBRC 2024 - XLII Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/sbrc.2024.1426>.
- RC2.D9** Danielle Fortunato, Silvia Ferreira, Patrícia Ferraz, Rafael Santos, and Daniel Leite. “**Rede Granular Convolutiva Evolutiva para Classificação de Fluxo de Imagens.**” In XXV Congresso Brasileiro de Automática (CBA), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15199672>
- RC2.D10** Caio Teixeira, Marco Aurélio Amaral Henriques. “**Desafios e oportunidades de pesquisa na adoção de criptografia pós-quântica em redes veiculares.**” In Anais do XXIV Simpósio Brasileiro de Segurança da Informação e de Sistemas Computacionais (SBSeg), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/sbseg.2024.241567>.
- RC2.D11** Thiago D. Ferreira, Renan C. A. Alves, Bruno C. Albertini, Marcos A. Simplicio Jr., Daniel M. Batista. “**Aplicação da Técnica Fuzzing em Testes da Implementação de Referência do SPDM.**” In Anais do XXIV Simpósio Brasileiro de Segurança da Informação e de Sistemas Computacionais (SBSeg), 2024. DOI: https://doi.org/10.5753/sbseg_estendido.2024.243284.
- RC2.D12** Rodrigo A. de A. Pierini, Caio Teixeira, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, Marco A. Amaral Henriques. “**Implementação e avaliação da cifra de fluxo Forro14 em hardware programável Tofino usando a linguagem P4.**” In Anais do XXIV Simpósio Brasileiro de Segurança da Informação e de Sistemas Computacionais (SBSeg), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/sbseg.2024.241483>.
- RC2.D13** Thiago D. Ferreira, Otavio Felipe de Freitas, Renan C. A. Alves, Bruno C. Albertini, Marcos A. Simplicio Jr., Daniel M. Batista. “**SPDM-WiD: Uma Ferramenta para Inspeção de Pacotes do Security Protocol Data Model (SPDM).**” In SBRC 2024 Salão de Ferramentas at In SBRC 2024 - XLII Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC), 2024. DOI: https://doi.org/10.5753/sbrc_estendido.2024.3175
- RC2.D14** Filipo Gabert Costa, Francisco Vogt, Fabricio Eduardo Rodriguez Cesen, Marcelo Caggiani Luizelli, Christian Esteve Rothenberg. “**Towards Time-Sensitive Networking Traffic Generation with PIPO-TG.**” In SBRC 2024 Salão de Ferramentas at SBRC 2024 - XLII Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC), 2024. DOI: https://doi.org/10.5753/sbrc_estendido.2024.3381.
- RC2.D15** Sergio Rossi da Silva, Francisco Vogt, Christian Esteve Rothenberg. “**Towards TSN-5G integration: simulating time synchronization through 5G via OMNeT++.**” In SBRC

2024 Salão de Ferramentas at SBRC 2024 - XLII Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (**SBRC**), 2024. DOI: https://doi.org/10.5753/sbrc_estendido.2024.3397.

RC2.D16 Matheus Lucas, Gabriel Nery, Karlla Rodrigues, Sand L. Correa and Fábio L. Verdi.. **“Uma avaliação empírica sobre o uso de WebAssembly para descarga de funções de realidade aumentada.”** In SBRC 2024 - XLII Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (**SBRC**), 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/sbrc.2024.1484>

E) Patents filed or IvDs submitted

RC2.E1 **Patent Reference Number:** PCT/EP2025/056322
Autors: Felipe A. S. Novais, Fábio Luciano Verdi, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, Gergely Pongrácz, Gyanesh Patra
Title: COMMUNICATION HANDLING
Status: Filed

F) Chapters in published books

RC2.F1 Marcelo Caggiani Luizelli, Francisco Vogt, Guilherme Mendes Vieira de Matos, Weverton Cordeiro, Alberto Egon Schaeffer-Filho, Marcos Schwarz, Fábio Luciano Verdi, and Christian Esteve Rothenberg. **“SmartNICs: The Next Leap in Networking.”** Capítulo de livro Mini Curso. In SBRC 2024 - XLII Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/sbc.15408.7.2>.

RC2.F2 Roberto Rodrigues-Filho, Eduardo S. Gama, Marcio Roberto Miranda Assis, Roger Immich, Edmundo Madeira, and Luiz Fernando Bittencourt. **“Content Steering: Leveraging the Computing Continuum to Support Adaptive Video Streaming.”** Capítulo de livro Mini Curso. In SBRC 2024 - XLII Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/sbc.15408.7.1>.

RC2.F3 Thiago Caproni Tavares, Leandro C. de Almeida, Washington Rodrigo Dias da Silva, Ariel Góes de Castro, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, and Fábio Luciano Verdi. **“Generation of Synthetic Datasets in the Context of Computer Networks using Generative Adversarial Networks.”** Capítulo de livro Mini Curso. In SBRC 2024 - XLII Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/sbc.15408.7.3>.

G) Books published

H) MSc Dissertations defended

RC2.H1 Sergio Rossi. **“Simulation of time synchronization and QoS mapping for TSN-5G integration.”** M.Sc. Dissertation, Universidade Estadual de Campinas. Advisor: Prof. Christian Esteve Rothenberg. January 2025.

RC2.H2 Arthur Simas. **“eZtunnel: An eBPF-based Traffic Acceleration Mechanism for Cloud-Native Infrastructures.”** M.Sc. Dissertation, Universidade Estadual de Campinas. Advisor: Prof. Christian Esteve Rothenberg. January 2025.

RC2.H3 Rodrigo Pierini. **“Design, implementação e avaliação de atestação remota distribuída em plano de dados programável.”** M.Sc. Dissertation, Universidade Estadual de Campinas. Advisor: Prof. Marco Aurelio Henriques Amaral. January 2025.

I) PhD Theses defended

- RC2.I1** Suneet Kumar Singh. **“Advanced Data Plane Techniques for 5G: Hardware-Accelerated Hybrid User Plane Functions and Intelligent Traffic Identification and Prioritization.”** Ph.D. Theses, Universidade Estadual de Campinas. Advisor: Prof. Christian Esteve Rothenberg. November 2024.
- RC2.I2** Fabricio Rodriguez. **“Low-latency in-network applications through programmable data planes.”** Ph.D. Theses, Universidade Estadual de Campinas. Advisor: Prof. Christian Esteve Rothenberg. July 2024.

J) List of papers prepared, submitted, and accepted for publication

Accepted

- RC2.J06** Raza Ul Mustafa, Md Tariqul Islam, and Christian Esteve Rothenberg. **“Investigating the Impact of Channel Metrics in 5G NSA and SA on Video Streaming QoE”**. IEEE Network Operations and Management Symposium (**NOMS**), 2025.
- RC2.J07** Guilherme Matos, Fábio L. Verdi, Washington Silva, and Andrew Williams. **“DECOMPOSER: Functional Decomposition and Distributed Execution of Monolithic Applications to Heterogeneous Resources”**. IEEE Network Operations and Management Symposium (**NOMS**), 2025.
- RC2.J08** Bernardo Pandolfi Costa, Heitor Henrique da Silva, Analucia S. Morales, Luiz F. Bittencourt, Alison R. Panisson, and Roberto Rodrigues-Filho. **“A Multi-agent Approach to Self-Distributing Systems”**. International Conference on Advanced Information Networking and Applications (**AINA**), 2025.
- RC2.J09** Arthur J. Simas, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, and Gergely Pongrácz. **“eSeMeshA: eBPF-based Service Mesh Acceleration for Cloud-Native Infrastructures”**. IEEE International Conference on Network Softwarization (**NetSoft**), 2025.
- RC2.J10** Fabricio Rodriguez Cesen, Francisco Germano Vogt, Marcelo Caggiani Luizelli, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, and Géza Szabó. **“Harnessing P4 for In-Network Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Collision Avoidance”**. IEEE International Conference on Network Softwarization (**NetSoft**), 2025.
- RC2.J11** Alireza Shirmarz, Mateus N. Bragatto, Fábio Luciano Verdi, Suneet Kumar Singh, Christian Rothenberg, Gyanesh Patra, and Gergely Pongrácz. **“In-Network AR/CG Traffic Classification Entirely Deployed in the Programmable Data Plane: Unlocking RTP Features and L4S Integration”**. IEEE International Conference on Network Softwarization (**NetSoft**), 2025.
- RC1.J12** Lucas Soares, Carlos Kamienski, Fabíola Oliveira, and Luiz Bittencourt. **“Edge4Drone: Managing Landings and Takeoffs in High-Density Distribution Centers”**. 18th International Workshop on Networked Robotics and Communication Systems (**NetRobiCS**), in conjunction with IEEE International Conference on Computer Communications (**INFOCOM**), 2025.
- RC2.J13** Rodrigo A. de A. Pierini, Caio Teixeira, Christian Esteve Rothenberg, and Marco Amaral Henriques. **“Implementação e avaliação da cifra de fluxo Xote em plano de dados de hardware programável Tofino”**. Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (**SBRC**), 2025.
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- RC2.J15** Alireza Shirmarz, Carlos Henrique França Marques, Fábio Luciano Verdi, Suneet Kumar Singh, and Christian Esteve Rothenberg. **"DCTPQ: Dynamic Cloud Gaming Traffic Prioritization Using Machine Learning and Multi-Queueing for QoE Enhancement"**. Simpósio Brasileiro de Redes de Computadores e Sistemas Distribuídos (SBRC), 2025.
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V. List of Abbreviations

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
6G	6th Generation
ABNT	Associação Brasileira de Normas Técnicas (Brazilian Association of Technical Standards)
ACM	Association for Computing Machinery
ADVENTURE	Adaptive and Secure Network Applications over the Industrial Internet
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AKMA	Authentication and Key Management for Applications
AMQP	Advanced Message Queuing Protocol
ANATEL	Agência Nacional de Telecomunicações (National Telecommunications Agency)
ANFIS	Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
B5G	Beyond 5G
BC	Benefício Complementar (Complementary Benefit)
BEPE	Scholarship for Research Internship Abroad
C3LA	Cognitive Closed Control Loops Architecture for Edge IoV Services
CA	Cognitive Architectures
CAD	Computer-Aided Design
CCL	Closed Control Loop
CEC	Customized Edge Computing
CCEN	Center for Exact and Natural Sciences
CG	Cloud Gaming
CISB	Brazil-Sweden Research and Innovation Centre
Co-PI	Co-Principal Investigator
CPE	Centro de Pesquisa em Engenharia (Engineering Research Center - ERC)
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DEMIST	Distributed Edge Computing Swarm Intelligence
DisCoNet	Distributed Computer Networking
DMTF	Distributed Management Task Force
DP	Differential Privacy
DPDK	Data Plane Development Kit
DPU	Data Processing Unit
DR	Doctorate
DT	Decision Tree
eBPF	Extended Berkeley Packet Filter
EAIP	Escritório de Apoio Institucional ao Pesquisador (Institutional Support Office for Researchers)
EC	Executive Committee
ECN	Explicit Congestion Notification
MBB	Mobile Broadband
EDC	Education and Dissemination Coordinator
EDD	Education and Dissemination Deputy
EDK	Education and Dissemination of Knowledge
EDKM	Education and Dissemination of Knowledge Manager
EM	Executive Manager
EPC	Evolved Packet Core
EPM	Executive Project Management
ER	Ericsson Research
ERC	Engineering Research Center
EU	European Union
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FAPESP	Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de São Paulo (São Paulo Research Foundation)
FCD	Fluid Control and Data Planes

FL	Federated Learning
FPGA	Field-Programmable Gate Array
GAN	Generative Adversarial Networks
GEO	Management, Structure, and Governance Plan
GO	Grant Office
GOOSE	Generic Object Oriented System Event
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HTC	Holographic-Type Communications
HW	Hardware
IAB	International Advisory Board
IBN	Intent-Based Networking
IC	Iniciação Científica” (Undergraduate Researcher)
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission's
IED	Intelligent Electronic Device
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IIIT	Indian Institute of Information Technology
INT	In-band Network Telemetry
INOVA	UNICAMP Innovation Agency
INPI	Instituto Nacional da Propriedade Industrial (National Institute of Industrial Property)
INT	n-Band Network Telemetry
IoRT	IoRT: Internet of Robotic Things
IoT	Internet of Things
IoV	Internet of Vehicles
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IR	Intermediary Representations
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITC	International Teletraffic Congress
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
ITU-T	International Telecommunication Union - Telecommunication Standardization Sector
IvD	Invention Disclosure
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
kTLS	kernel Transport Layer Security
L4S	Low Latency, Low Loss, Scalable Throughput
LCA	Laboratory of Control and Automation
LEMAC	Laboratory of Applied and Computational Electromagnetism
LLM	Large Language Model
LGPD	Brazilian General Data Protection Law
MAR	Mobile Augmented Reality
MBB	Mobile Broadband
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
ML	Machine Learning
MMS	Manufacturing Message Specification
MNS	Multiscale Network Systems
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
MSc	Master of Sciences
NEWTON	iN Edge netWork indusTrial automatioN
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NOMS	Network Operations and Management Symposium
NSF	National Science Foundation
NTR	Nothing To Report

ONF	Open Networking Foundation
ONAP	Open Network Automation Platform
ONF	Open Networking Foundation
O-RAN	Open Radio Access Network
P4	Programming Protocol-independent Packet Processors
PA	In Portuguese “Pesquisador Associado”, in English “Associate Researcher”
PCAP	Packet Capture
PCT	Patent Cooperation Treaty
PD	In Portuguese “Pesquisador de Doutorado”, in English “Doctoral Researcher”
PI	Principal Investigator
PIPE	Support Program for Research in Small Businesses
PITE	Research Partnership for Technological Innovation Program
PP	In Portuguese “Pesquisador Principal”, in English “Principal Researcher”
PPC	Partnership Coordinator
PPDG	Postdoctoral Scholarship Subprogram in Research Management
PoC	Proof of Concept
PRP	Pro-Rectorate of Research
PTT	Plan for Technology Transfer
QKD	Quantum Key Distribution
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
QUIC	Quick UDP Internet Connections
RAN	Radio Access Network
RA	Research Area
RC1	Second SMARTNESS Scientific Report
REDK2	Second SMARTNESS Education and Dissemination of Knowledge Report
RF	Radiofrequency
RGE02	Second SMARTNESS Governance Report
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RNP	In Portuguese “Rede Nacional de Ensino e Pesquisa”, in English “Brazilian network for education and research”
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RS	Research Strand
RTT2	Second SMARTNESS Technology Transfer Report
SA	Stand Alone
SAGe	FAPESP online system
SAM	Humanoid Agent
SBOM	Software Bill of Materials
SBRC	Brazilian Symposium on Computer Networks
SCI	UNICAMP Institutional Communication Secretariat
SEM	SMARTNESS Entanglement Meetings
SDN	Software-Defined Networking
SFC	Service Function Chaining
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
SLSA	Supply Chain Levels for Software Artifacts
SMARTNESS	Smart Networks and Services for 2030
SmartNIC	Smart Network Interface Card
SMO	Service Management and Orchestration
SNS	Smart Networks and Services
SPDM	Security Protocol and Data Model
STA	Scientific and Technology Advancement

STAB	STA Board
SUS	Sustainability
SV	Sampled Values
SW	Software
TBD	To Be Defined
TDRP	Truck-Drone Routing Problem
TFHE	Fast Fully Homomorphic Encryption over the Torus
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TPU	Tensor Processing Unit
TRU	Trustworthiness: Security, Privacy, Safety, Ethics
TSN	Time-Sensitive Networking
TT	Technology Transfer
TTC	Technology Transfer Coordinator
TTD	Technology Transfer Deputy
TTI	Technology Transfer and Innovation
TTM	Technology Transfer Manager
TSN	Time-Sensitive Networking
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UFABC	Federal University of ABC
UFAM	Federal University of Amazonas
UFBA	Federal University of Bahia
UFC	Federal University of Ceará
UFMG	Federal University of Minas Gerais
UNICAMP	Universidade Estadual de Campinas (State University of Campinas)
UNIPAMPA	Universidade Federal do Pampa
UNISINOS	Universidade do Vale do Rio dos Sinos
UFPA	Federal University of Pará
UFPE	Federal University of Pernambuco
UFRGS	Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul
UFRN	Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte
UFSCar	Federal University of São Carlos
UFSC	Federal University of Santa Catarina
UFU	Federal University of Uberlândia
UG	Undergrad
UE	User Equipment
UPF	User Plane Function
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable and Low-Latency Communications
USP	Universidade Estadual de São Paulo (State University of São Paulo)
VR	Virtual Reality
VNA	Vector Network Analyzer
WASM	WebAssembly
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
XR	Extended Reality
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project

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